

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for **African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.**

AfriConEU Networking Academy

D4.1 Implementation Plan

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Glossary and Abbreviations	
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

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Executive Summary

The AfriConEU Networking Academy is an innovative mechanism for connecting and sharing knowledge, good practices, experiences and resources between DIHs in Africa and between DIHs in Africa and EU, in a comprehensive, replicable and self-sustaining way. Through two flagship programmes, the AfriConEU Networking Academy aims to empower and enable African DIHs to best serve their local industry, boost their start-up ecosystems and empower the youth population with the necessary skills to thrive in a digitalized world.

This deliverable (*D4.1. Implementation Plan*) has been developed to support, organise and plan the implementation of the numerous activities and events that will be offered by the AfriConEU Academy during the next months.

The plan presented in this deliverable covers all planning and organizing aspects of the AfriConEU Networking Academy activities. After briefly presenting in section 1 the project and describing the objectives and methodology, the deliverable provides, in section 2, an overview of all the 46 planned activities that will be delivered as part of the two Flagship Programmes of the AfriConEU Academy, namely the Capacity Building Programme and the Transcontinental Partnership Development Programme. It also provides a preliminary timeline for the delivery of all the activities and events that have been created with the cooperation of all partners.

Then, section 3 presents the core of the deliverable providing information and guidelines on the necessary organisational aspects and logistics to successfully deliver the Networking Academy activities, and to attract and engage participants. Planning Templates have been completed for each Academy activity, offering a first overview of the implementation activities.

The deliverable also offers specific guidance for partners to ensure a proper follow-up of each of the Academy events. This can be found in section 4, where KPIs, Milestones, Risks and mitigation measures have been defined to monitor and report the progress and success of the Academy.

In section 5, an overview of partners' roles is presented to support and clarify partners concerning their responsibilities. An "Implementation Support Mechanism" was also designed to ensure support is provided to partners.

Finally, the deliverable includes, in its annexes, practical and useful templates that will support partners with their implementation tasks. These include an event invitation template; an agenda template; a planning template with checklists; and most importantly a Monitoring Template which is an essential document for reporting the implementation of each Academy activity.

1. Introduction

1.1. About AfriConEU

The AfriConEU project is being developed in the framework of the EU's efforts to digitalize the economy and the industry. Since 2016 the EU invests in the creation and support of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) as the main structure for supporting the digital transformation of European businesses. The AfriConEU project aims at enhancing the capacity of African DIHs to accelerate the digital transformation of the African economy and society. To achieve this goal, an innovative mechanism is being created: the AfriConEU Networking Academy, a transcontinental academy for DIHs in Africa and Europe, which will offer two Flagship Programmes: (i) one dedicated to Capacity Building for reinforcing the role of African DIHs as innovation intermediaries, matching demand and offer of digital services and technologies and supporting digital entrepreneurs; (ii) another dedicated to Transcontinental Partnership Development between DIHs, start-ups, entrepreneurs, investors, etc. from both continents. These programmes were developed considering the needs of African DIHs and the innovation ecosystems of the targeted African countries. Specifically, the AfriConEU programmes were developed through a collaborative design process in which both African and European DIHs, experts, and innovators were challenged to share their experience and brainstorm, discuss and pin-point the DIHs' training needs¹.

1.2. Objectives of D4.1

This deliverable was developed in the context of WP4, which has the following objectives:

- to organise the delivery of the Capacity Building and Partnership Development programmes of the AfriConEU Networking Academy and ensure their smooth and unhindered implementation and uptake from DIHs
- to monitor and assess their implementation and, based on the information and insight obtained, to validate, update and calibrate the AfriConEU Networking Academy programmes, tools and resources

D4.1 aims at creating a detailed implementation and monitoring plan that specifies all foreseen activities of the AfriConEU Networking Academy. In concrete, it aims to provide:

- a **step-by-step guide and planning** of the implementation activities to deliver the Capacity Building and Transcontinental Partnership Development programmes
- a common **strategy** and approach for engaging, recruiting, and enrolling participants in the activities of the AfriConEU Networking Academy
- an overview of the **monitoring and assessment** strategy to enable partners to plan, collect data and prepare for any unforeseen circumstances
- **useful and practical templates** for organising, promoting and monitoring the AfriConEU Academy programmes.

¹ More details on the designing process can be found in deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4, D3.5.

By doing so, this deliverable aims at supporting partners to be efficient, by channelling their efforts and time in the right direction, leading to successful project completion. A plan that will smoothen the process of organizing and implementing for all involved partners. This shared plan will boost communication since it will keep AfriConEU partners on the same page. It will map implementation risks and make them manageable. It will work as a compass to keep all partners focused on AfriConEU objectives making collaboration more fluid.

Therefore, the main **target audience** of D4.1 includes the AfriConEU consortium members, and associate partners. A secondary target audience includes other stakeholders such as the wider Horizon Europe community since D4.1 constitutes itself a tool that allows the organisation, coordination and implementation of complex project activities.

1.3. Methodology

This deliverable builds upon the outcomes of WP3. It combines all the planning from *D3.1. Capacity Building Flagship Programme*, *D3.2. Structure and training material for local workshops*, *D3.3. Webinars Content and Design*, *D3.4. Inventory of capacity building resources and ready to use training material*, *D3.5. Online Masterclass* and *D3.6. Trans-Continental Partnership Building Flagship Programme* and offers the necessary strategies, tools and resources to transform WP3 goals into action.

The methodology that was used for developing this deliverable was based on the collaborative design process, in which all AfriConEU partners were involved, under the coordination of the partner Stimuli. The process was comprised by the organisation of dedicated meetings and discussions with all partners where the different Academy activities were further brainstormed and defined, aiming to make the programmes and activities designed within WP3 (D3.1 to D3.6) more concrete. The partners leading the implementation of the activities were, thus, challenged to define and provide detailed planning regarding the different AfriConEU Networking Academy activities, by completing the planning templates included in section 3 of this deliverable. In parallel, partners were asked to further discuss the most appropriate ways for delivering, engaging, increasing participation, monitoring, and assessing the activities. The partners' contributions were incorporated into this deliverable's content. Through this methodology, everyone was encouraged to get their thoughts out and put their ideas into an accessible place and then turn them into a product of participatory work. By involving all partners, it was possible not only to define activities that reflect the needs and ambitions of the different entities, but also to design a programme that offers different knowledge and skills following a cohesive and structured planning.

2. Overview of the AfriConEU Networking Academy Flagship Programmes

The AfriConEU Networking Academy aims to facilitate knowledge and experience sharing between African and European DIHs, drive the development of mutually beneficial partnerships and support the creation of collective projects for boosting the digital economy, empowering youth and women and fostering innovation and growth. Through two Flagships Programmes, one dedicated to Capacity Building for DIHs and another dedicated to Transcontinental Partnerships Development, the Networking Academy will empower African DIHs to best serve their local industry, boost their innovation ecosystem, support the scale-up of African start-ups and empower the youth population with the necessary skills to thrive in a digitalized world. It will also reinforce cooperation between the African and European DIHs in areas of mutual interest, such as investments, matching skilled workforce to the needs of the market, and contributing to the Sustainable Development Goals. These two programmes will be delivered through a rich set of activities, including workshops, webinars, masterclasses, brokerage events, bootcamps and capitalisation events (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Overview of AfriConEU Networking Academy activities

2.1. Capacity Building Programme

This section presents an overview of the Capacity Building Flagship Programme. This programme is composed of four sub-programmes, namely: 1. Capacity building in **business development models** and **multi-actor approach**; 2. Capacity building in **Technology transfer of innovative technologies**; 3. Capacity building on **start-up's financial support**; 4. Capacity building in **digital and entrepreneurial skills development**. These sub-programmes will be delivered through a rich set of webinars, workshops and masterclasses as illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 2 - AfriConEU Capacity Building Flagship Programme: sub-programmes and activities

The first capacity building sub-programme will be delivered through 5 interactive webinars, 3 workshops and 2 online masterclasses targeting African and European DIHs with the aim to help them develop effective business models and strategies contributing to their sustainability. The following table presents the thematic focus of these capacity building activities.

Table 1 - Capacity building activities of the sub-programme “Business development models and multi-actor approach”

CAPACITY BUILDING SUB-PROGRAMME 1: Business Development and Multi-actor Approach	Webinars	DIH Strategy and Strategy Resources
		DIH Business Models
		The Business Model Navigator
		Building a Business Plan
		Sustainability in DIHs
	Local Workshops	Tailor-made strategies for DIH
		Business Model Canvas Template and Instructions
		Lean Canvas Template and Instructions
	Masterclasses	Case study of successful DIHs – Part 1
		Case study of successful DIHs – Part 2

The second sub-programme will be delivered through webinars, hybrid workshops and online masterclasses with the aim to help participants develop their knowledge and skills in the technology transfer process. The following table presents the thematic focus of these capacity building activities.

Table 2 - Capacity building activities of the sub-programme “Technology transfer of innovative technologies”

CAPACITY BUILDING SUB-PROGRAMME 2: Technology transfer of innovative technologies	Webinars	Navigating through the Intellectual Property maze
		Leverage start-up creation from innovative technology
		Fast-tracking technologies to market
		Data-driven innovation
		Business Intelligence and Analytics
	Local Workshops	The Technology Transfer Process
		The Technology Valorization Process
		The Market Uptake Process
	Masterclasses	Lessons from European start-ups
		Business Intelligence and Analytics

The third sub-programme will be delivered through webinars, hybrid workshops and online masterclasses with the aim to help participants develop their financial support services. The following table presents the thematic focus of these capacity building activities.

Table 3 - Capacity building activities of the sub-programme “Start-ups financial support”

CAPACITY BUILDING SUB-PROGRAMME 3: Start-ups financial support	Webinars	Durable Funding Sources for DIHs
		Phases of Investment
		Crowdfunding and Microcredit
		Impact Investing and Subsidized Finance
		Valuations of Projects, Financial Management, Projections
	Local Workshops	Bootstrapping, Revenue Models and Managerial Accounting
		Preparing for Investment and Investor Relationships
		Building and Using a Network of Funding Source
	Masterclasses	Essentials of Innovation Finance
		Financing Digital Innovation Hubs

The fourth sub-programme will be delivered through webinars, workshops and masterclasses with the aim to help DIHs develop digital and entrepreneurial skills development programmes, increase participation of women entrepreneurs in innovation programmes. The following table presents the thematic focus of these capacity building activities.

Table 4 - Capacity building activities of the sub-programme “Digital and entrepreneurial skills development”

CAPACITY BUILDING SUB-PROGRAMME 4: Digital and entrepreneurial skills development	Webinars	Gender lens innovation
		Bridging the gap between offline and online marketing
		Purpose-driven DIH
		Impact Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning
		Collaborate to Innovate
	Local Workshops	Gender lens innovation
		Digital marketing for successful businesses
		Purpose-driven DIH
	Masterclasses	Gender-lens finance
		Building a Theory of Change

More detailed descriptions about the training purpose, content and materials of these sub-programmes and capacity building activities are available in the following deliverables: D3.1, D3.2, D3.3 and D3.5.

2.2. Transcontinental Partnership Development Programme

The second Flagship Programme of the AfriConEU Networking Academy is the Transcontinental Partnership Development programme. This programme includes four sub-programmes that will be delivered through one International Brokerage Event, four design thinking bootcamps, and a final Capitalisation event.

Figure 3 - AfriConEU Transcontinental Partnership Development Flagship Programme: sub-programmes and activities

The following tables summarise all these activities and briefly present their format, content, goals and target groups.

Table 5 - Transcontinental Partnership Development Flagship Programme: International Brokerage Event

International Brokerage Event	
Aim	To hold interactive and networking activities on site, such as round tables and breakout sessions to cultivate collaborations between start-ups, European and African DIHs and other participants. Activities will touch upon all the Transcontinental Partnership sub-programmes.
Target group	Investors, support networks, startups entrepreneurs, DIH teams, African-European diaspora communities
Format	2 days duration, Hybrid format on site and remote hubs collaborating with main event

Table 6 - Transcontinental Partnership Development Flagship Programme: Design thinking bootcamps

Design Thinking Bootcamps	
Aim	The connections made during the International Brokerage Event will be further supported to continue and evolve with the organisation of 4 design thinking bootcamps that will take place in each one of the targeted African countries (Ghana, Uganda, Nigeria, Tanzania) aiming to bring together digital ecosystem stakeholders and experts from Europe and Africa and facilitate knowledge and experience sharing towards common projects development.
Target group	Mixed teams: African and European DIHs, start-ups and enterprises, Individuals who have not participated in the Brokerage Event can participate in the bootcamps
Format	Duration: 3 days Face to face (possibly hybrid)

Table 7 - Transcontinental Partnership Development Flagship Programme: Capitalisation and celebration event

Capitalisation and Celebration Event	
Aim	At the end of the project, a final Capitalisation and Celebration Event will be organised to bring together DIHs, experts, researchers, policy makers from both continents and follow up and capitalise upon the connections created and the results achieved. The event will also reflect upon the achievements of AfriConEu, explore new opportunities for innovation generated and support policy uptake.
Target group	European and African DIHs, experts, researchers, policy makers, ICT-58 Family representatives
Format	Single, multi-day event possibly organized in parallel with or as a component of a larger technology and innovation event

More detailed descriptions about the activities of the Partnership Development Flagship Programme are available in deliverable D3.6.

2.3. Timeline of the AfriConEU Flagship Programmes

The AfriConEU Networking Academy Flagships Programmes will be delivered through **46 activities/events** that will take place between **May 2022 (M16) and October 2023 (M33)**. When designing the timeline for delivering these activities, partners took into consideration the following issues:

- The timeline offers a comprehensive learning journey for participants;
- The timeline enables participants to participate in all thematic sub-programmes;
- Overlaps between different AfriConEU activities and partners responsibilities are avoided;
- Clashes with public holidays and with days close to public holidays or close to activities that might be of interest to their participants are avoided;
- Activities are delivered within major international days or events whose topics are relevant to AfriConEU, such as the Global Entrepreneurship Week.

Taking the above into account, partners jointly defined the timeline for the delivery of the AfriConEU Networking Academy programmes. The timeline is a relevant tool both for organisation and communication purposes, supporting partners to direct their efforts over time and having a concrete and close communication with the project audiences. It intends also to be as flexible as necessary, allowing for adjustments depending on the circumstances, such as the ongoing pandemic and the possibility for co-organization of events.

NETWORKING ACADEMY TIMELINE

Figure 4 - AfriConEU Networking Academy Timeline 2022-2023

3. Implementation planning

This section presents the activities planning made by partners to effectively deliver the AfriConEU Flagship Programmes. It starts with an overview of the strategy that will be followed for engaging target groups and encouraging their participation, then it briefly describes some key organisational aspects for organising the activities and finally presents detailed implementation plans for each of the 46 activities that will be delivered.

3.1. Engagement of participants

A key element to ensuring the success of the AfriConEU Networking Academy programmes is the effective attraction and engagement of participants. To this end, the project has developed a specific Stakeholders Engagement Strategy that is detailed in **D4.2 - Engagement strategy and activities reported**. To support partners in having an overview of the engagement strategy, a summary is presented below. This summary does not replace, the consultation of D4.2, which remains the key tool to be followed when planning, implementing and reporting engagement activities.

The engagement strategy has three main phases that comprise the core AfriConEU efforts to attract the attention of stakeholders towards the Networking Academy activities, and a fourth phase aiming to ensure the continuous implementation of activities that motivate the active engagement and motivation of stakeholders on the Academy events. The figure below summarizes the engagement strategy phases.

Figure 5 - AfriConEU Stakeholders Engagement Strategy

Several methods and tools will be employed to ensure stakeholders are appropriately informed and engaged to participate in the AfriConEU Academy activities ranging from interactive engagement sessions to social media campaigns, press releases, and invitations. The table below lists the engagement actions that must be implemented by all partners. Specific actions were also defined and those shall be consulted in D4.2.

Engagement activities to be implemented by all partners (from M16 to M33)

Inviting participants [ALL PARTNERS]

Invitations shall be sent to relevant stakeholders:

- ✓ **open invitations** published and communicated to stakeholders both inside and outside partners' networks
- ✓ **invitations sent by partners to stakeholders** already involved in their networks and communities.

In **Annex 1**, it is provided an Invitation Email Template which can be used to invite participants.

Registering participants [PARTNERS COORDINATING ACTIVITIES' ORGANISATION]

- ✓ Each partner coordinating the organisation and delivering a specific Academy activity will be responsible for preparing the online registration form, with INOVA, and informing the project's dissemination leader (YMH) and the rest of the consortium (through email). **Registration forms shall be published at least 1 month before the event.**
- ✓ Partners shall use **Eventbrite** for creating the online registration form as this platform is well-known by the audiences and allows linking the several events to the same organiser, which will support the promotion efforts. **An Eventbrite account was created for the project and all partners are asked to use it** or, at least, to list AfriConEU account as one of the organizers of the event (applicable, for instance, when the Academy activity is organised within a major event).
- ✓ The registration forms must contain an activity description covering the 5Ws, the activity agenda and a brief presentation of AfriConEU project and the consortium to contextualize the activity:
 - WHAT is the event about?
 - WHY it is important to attend?
 - WHO is organizing and who should register?
 - WHERE does it take place?
 - WHEN does it take place?
 - AGENDA
 - AfriConEU project and consortium (incl. disclaimer)
- ✓ The activity description must clearly identify the funding from the EC, by including the following disclaimer and EC logo:

AfriConEU project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (GA no. 101016687).

- ✓ Furthermore, the registration forms must ask for the following information to participants:
 - Full Name
 - Gender (Options: Women; Man; Non-binary & Other)
 - E-mail
 - Country
 - Company/Organization
 - Sector
 - Type of Organization (Options: Accelerator; Large Enterprise; SME; DIHUB; Entrepreneur; Investor; Start-up; Other)
 - I would like to receive AfriConEU newsletter (Options: Yes/No)
 - I would like to keep being informed about AfriConEU Networking Academy activities by email (regular information on agenda, dates and places) (Options: Yes/No)

Follow-up [PARTNERS COORDINATING ACTIVITIES' ORGANISATION]

- ✓ Reminders and final confirmation requests shall be sent to registered participants in order to ensure the participation of stakeholders and accommodate changes concerning their involvement. This is especially relevant in the case of physical activities and events where only a limited number of stakeholders will be able to participate onsite. Furthermore, in cases of high interest for participation, a reserve list shall be developed to reduce the risk of limited participation in case people fail to confirm their attendance in time. Activity organisers are encouraged to follow-up with participants (by email, direct contacts, etc.), at least, 1 week before the planned activity to confirm their participation. In case of onsite events, the confirmed participants will be requested to provide logistical details, such as dietary requirements of participants, transport mode they plan to use, etc.

➔ To consult D4.2 to confirm detailed engagement strategy and activities to be implemented.

3.2. Communication and dissemination actions

Besides the engagement strategy, the success of AfriConEU Networking Academy relies on the planning and implementation of a good communication and dissemination strategy. Apart from the regular promotion activities implemented (presented and reported in *D6.1* and *D6.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan and Report*), AfriConEU has defined a specific strategy to promote the Networking Academy events.

#Website

All Academy activities will be promoted in AfriConEU website. Specific and catchy contents and formats will be created to attract the attention of users, guide them among the different Academy activities and trigger their registration and participation. One of the tools that will be used are the pop-ups, as shown in the figure below, which will highlight the next event, providing the date, venue and a call-to-action button to quickly direct users to the registration form.

Figure 6 - AfriConEU website: pop-up triggering the attention to activities

Activities announcements will be also published in the [What's New](#) section of the website, including a short description and information for registration.

#Social media

AfriConEU Networking Academy will be also promoted in the project social media. Specifically, before each forthcoming activity, there will be a specific communication process that will be implemented mostly through Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook. The content of the posts will depend on the nature and context of the forthcoming activity. Concretely, each activity will be promoted with 3-4 key posts: **(i)** the first post will be introductory, announcing the upcoming event and including the dates and the format (physical, digital or hybrid); **(ii)** then, some posts (1-2) will focus on the activity's theme and the speakers; **(iii)** and, finally, close to the activity (one or two days before), a post will be published to remind the registered or potential participants about the event and motivates them to take part. During the events, a live coverage will be done in Twitter.

To ensure the successful promotion of the Academy activities, all partners are requested to contribute to communication and dissemination activities. The table below lists the actions that must be implemented by partners.

Table 9 - Communication activities to be implemented by all partners, along AfriConEU Networking Academy implementation (M16-M33)

Communication activities to be implemented by all partners (from M16 to M33)

Files² to keep *always updated* [PARTNERS COORDINATING ACTIVITIES ORGANISATION]

Partners coordinating Academy activities are requested to keep always updated and to complete:

- ✓ **Academy activities control file** — excel file “AfriConEU Time Plan and Control Point”. This file contains the following fields to be completed:
 - Date of the activity;
 - Activity Type (workshop, webinar, etc.);
 - Title of the activity;
 - Location of the event (in case of hybrid event, the physical location must be also provided);
 - Main organiser of the activity (i.e. implementation responsible);
 - Partner responsible for the activity design;
 - Partners who will help the delivering of the activity;
 - Suggestions for speakers, trainers and other guests;
 - Confirmed speakers, trainers and other guests;
 - Links to training materials;
 - Link to registration form.
- ✓ **Academy Planning Templates** (section 3.3 of this deliverable). These will be used to create contents to promote the activities in the project website and social media.

Timeline for closing and release of information [PARTNERS COORDINATING ACTIVITIES ORGANISATION]

- ✓ **At least 2 months before the event**, the information below shall be closed and communicated to YMH, INOVA and the rest of the consortium (by email):
 - Date, location, general title/ theme and a preliminary paragraph presenting the activity;
 - Speakers, moderators and other guests (the first confirmations), their photos (with high resolution) and URL to CV (webpage);
 - First version of activity agenda;
 - First version of registration form, with disclaimer (check engagement activities, in section 3.1, for type of information requested for registration forms).
- ✓ **At least 1 month before the event**, the information below shall be closed and communicated to YMH, INOVA and the rest of the consortium (by email):
 - Registration form fully described, covering the 5Ws, Titles, Agenda, AfriConEU project and partners, and disclaimer;
 - Speakers, moderators and other guests, their photos (with high resolution), URL to CV (webpage) and short sentence presenting them;
 - Activity Agenda, including short presentation of each topic addressed.

The partner **YMH** (AfriConEU communication and dissemination leader) will be responsible for:

- uploading the contents in the AfriConEU website;
- promoting the activities in social media;
- covering the events live on Twitter;
- creating the visuals required for each event (images to be shared on social media and other visuals) to ensure the branding coherence.

² Available in the project shared folder.

3.3. Organisational and logistics aspects

Before presenting the detailed activities planning, some transversal aspects shall be considered by organisers when planning and implementing the activities.

The **first** issue is related to the **type of participants expected for each activity**. All the AfriConEU Academy activities and events will be open to interested stakeholders from both Africa and Europe. These include representatives of the African and European digital innovation ecosystems, experts from European DIHs and Pan-African networks dedicated to enforcing DIHs, entrepreneurs and investors, members of the African diaspora community, and start-ups in Africa and Europe. As part of WP3 tasks and deliverables, potential participants have already been defined for each of the Networking Academy Activities to ensure alignment with the learning objectives and outcomes of each activity. In addition, the participant profiles for each activity are briefly described in the detailed implementation plans presented in the following sub-section. Nevertheless, during the organisation phase of each activity, all partners are encouraged to consider additional aspects of the profile of participants, such as their actual role in the organisation they represent (i.e., manager, trainer, consultant etc.) and the years of experience they have in the field of entrepreneurship and innovation support. This will support the identification, design and delivering of training aligned with the needs and profiles of participants.

The **second** aspect relates to the **space where the event will take place**. AfriConEU activities and events are planned to take place online, on-site and hybrid. Regarding physical activities, for the selection of the venues, organisers should consider several aspects that will be determined by the specificities and needs of each case. For instance, organisers should ensure that the chosen venues provide the required infrastructure for the event's optimal conduct, such as **i)** availability of appropriate technical infrastructure; **ii)** sufficient space to hold the number of invited participants and the activities to be performed; **iii)** appropriate lighting and adequate air circulation; **iv)** Accessible location (availability of local transportation, accessible parking etc.).

In the case of hybrid events, in addition to the above requirements, organisers should ensure that appropriate measures are taken to guarantee a wider and active engagement of participants in the activities. For that purpose, the following logistical details should be planned ahead: (i) screen through which participants following from home can be broadcasted (when applicable); (ii) interactive tools that will match tools and materials used on-site should be provided; (iii) any recording system should be set-up and tested before the event.

The **third** aspect that shall be considered are the measures of each territory/ space concerning the ongoing **Covid-19 pandemic**. Organisers must follow the latest official guidelines and ensure activities are compliant to those measures.

Finally, to guarantee the success of the plans, at least one check-in and one test meeting shall be organised before each event.

CHECK AND TEST MEETINGS

At least:

- ✓ Check-in meeting: 1 week before the event;
- ✓ Testing meeting: 1 day before the event.

3.4. Detailed plan of activities

In this section, the detailed plans of the AfriConEU Academy activities are presented. In overall, for planning the activities, a common strategy was agreed upon among the partners and followed. This strategy challenged partners to discuss and identify i) the organisers and facilitators of activities; ii) collaborations with external speakers and trainers for delivering the activities; iii) further detail activities as defined by WP3; iv) list existing training materials that will be reused during the activities and/or offer the flexibility to external speakers and trainers to use their own training material. This innovative format will contribute to the flexibility and future sustainability and exploitation of the AfriConEU Academy programmes.

The results are presented next, ordered chronologically by the date of delivery of the activities. Considering that the AfriConEU Academy activities will run for a long period (May 2022 (M16) – October 2023(M33)), the planning of some activities is preliminary and updates will be added.

AfriConEU Networking Academy

Detailed planning

2022

#1 Local Workshop: Purpose Drive DIH

May 2022

Organised as a physical event in Dodoma (Tanzania) by Buni, on 13 May 2022 as part of Tanzania Innovation Week

Workshop organisation and facilitation team:

Main moderator: Ms. Patience Abraham – who is the Hub Manager of Buni that runs the Hub of Hubs strategy. Buni’s experience in mentoring other hubs and its participation in the Southern African Innovation Collective makes it a perfect partner for running this.

Invited speakers/trainers:
Dr. Chitundu Kasese – Director, National Technology Business Centre, Zambia
Patrick Krappie – Ag. CEO, Technology Innovation Agency, South Africa
Budzanani Tacheba – Director, Innovation, Technology Science and Technology Park, Botswana
Ms. Sina Legong – Corporate & Programs Manager, mLab South Africa
Lovisa Kambonde – Immanuel, National Commission on Research, Science and Technology, Namibia
Topic 2 trainer: Tandokazi Nquma – Moyo: Innovation, Management & Business Development at Technology Innovation Agency, South Africa

To run hands-on exercise in DIH to define their activity, purpose, roles and processes.

Rapporteur: Marina Shio will be responsible for the registration of the participants and setting up the equipment for Livestreaming.

Target groups / participants

- 60 Participants will be invited. In particular, all Local DIH managers will be invited as this is important for them in strategic building. It is something that they have requested in previous Hubs Meet Up. Participants will be from Tanzania, Ghana, Namibia, Botswana, and South Africa. But the workshop will be geared for the local Tanzanian DIH.

- Participating Hubs will be sent direct invitations to attend the workshop. 2 members per each hub are expected to attend.

Venue and other organisational aspects

The venue will be at Buni Hub with a possibility of virtual livestreaming. Buni is central for the Hub activities given its connection to COSTECH and as partner of Innovation Week Tanzania.

Training material to be used:

Panel Discussion with African DIHs

Worksheet on strategy for DIH:

<https://smartfactories.eu/uploads/7b848e7ce7c6a2a9222acbfa4a18577a3fcd7019.xlsx>

Draft Agenda:

Activity	Description	Time	Person Responsible
Exploring the African Ecosystem: DIH	Panel Discussion led by the moderator on the Innovation Ecosystem in Tanzania: Challenges and How to overcome them	10am – 11am	Moderator: Patience
Defining the DIH Purpose	Each DIH mapping their ecosystem. Rate the importance of the stakeholders mapped Analyse the current levels of engagement	11am – 13pm	Facilitator: Tandokazi
	COCKTAILS & NETWORKING		

#2 Webinar: DIH Strategy and Strategy Resources

May 2022

Organised online by ITC, on 18 May 2022

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main **moderator**: tbc

Facilitators: Someone from ITC team or someone selected by them

Invited **speakers/trainers**: tbc, strategy development specialists.

Rapporteur: From ITC. Also, in the registration form, a specific field to give consent to record the session and take pictures is going to be included.

Target groups / Participants

>50 participants will be invited (target 15 participants) representing DIHs managers from Africa. The goal of this webinar is that participants will learn the theory about strategy for DIHs, learn to use the tools for strategy development, and combine theory with the strategic vision of their own DIH. For that reason, this webinar is specially targeted at DIHs managers.

Participants will be engaged through open invitations published through the project website; social media (paid and unpaid); as well as through direct invitations from partners contacts; European DIH will be reached to provide specific African contacts

Venue and other organisational aspects

The Webinar will be organised through Zoom. Interactive tools such as Mentimeter/ Jamboard and Breakout rooms will be used.

Training material to be used:

The material used will be mainly a PowerPoint presentation but additional material such as videos and case studies (ready to use training resources) may be used if the trainer considers them relevant. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda:

To be defined by the trainer. It will include topics such as: Defining strategy, DIH & strategy, Strategy Development Process, Strategic Plan, Strategy Development Tools.

#3 Masterclass: Sustainable business development, lessons learnt**June 2022**

Organised online by ITC, on 8 June 2022

Masterclass organisation and facilitation team:

Main Presenter/Trainer: From ITC: Sustainability expert, circular economy expert, practitioners on the field of sustainable business development

Facilitator (if needed): ITC team

Rapporteur: From ITC. In the registration form, consent to record the session and take pictures should be included.

Target groups / Participants:

>50 participants will be invited (target 25 for each masterclass) representing DIH managers, as the content of this masterclass will be sustainable solutions and integration of sustainability into the business through sustainable development opportunities and why we need sustainable development.

Participants will be from Europe (30%) and from Africa (70%). Participants will be engaged through open invitations published through the project website; social media as well as through direct invitations from partners contacts;

Venue and other organisational aspects:

The Masterclass will be organised through Zoom. Interactive tools such as Mentimeter/ Jamboard and Breakout rooms will be used.

Training material to be used:

PowerPoint presentations, Examples from case studies, canvases for sustainable business models, best practice examples from DIH. The lecturer will prepare these materials and upload them onto the online repository of the project.

Draft Agenda:

This masterclass will focus on integrating sustainability into businesses as a central part of their way of doing business to increase profitability. As the market changes and customers and society search for more sustainable solutions, new sustainable opportunities arise, so we need to understand the broader system along the current and future value chain and transform it beyond the regulatory framework and ensure that ambitions are sustainable and valuable for the organisations as well as for the broader scope.

#4 Local Workshop: DIH Strategy and Strategy Resources**June 2022**

Organised as a HYBRID event in Kumasi by HAPA, on 9 June 2022

Workshop organisation and facilitation team:

Main moderator: *Gideon Brefo* (introduce the workshop, speakers and all other activities that takes place at the workshop. He is to ensure that all participants leave the workshop with key take away) Gideon has over a decade experience working in the entrepreneurial ecosystem and 17 years' experience in the corporate world. He has successfully built two businesses, Hapaweb Solutions and hapaSpace Innovation Hub. He is an IT enthusiast that seeks to develop innovative solutions. He is a certified British Council trainer, mentor and coach.

Invited speakers/trainers: Josiah K Eyison is the CEO and Co-Founder of the iSpace Foundation and a Consultant. In 2012, Josiah co-founded the Space Foundation and has since led interventions that have supported more than 3500 individuals (approximately 65% women) in West Africa, East Africa, and the United Kingdom with technology-focused skills training for children and adults as well as business development and entrepreneurship training and mentoring.

Rapporteur: Philipina B Appiah (Bilingual Vlogger and Project Lead, SmartWoman Project): Philipina is an avid reader and a passionate writer. She has acquired a wealth of experience in project management and business development as she worked with the British Council, Hapaweb Solutions and hapaSpace Innovation Hub.

Target groups / Participants:

50 participants to be invited.

- 2 members from 23 DIHs
- Director of Programmes from the National Entrepreneurship and innovation Plan (NEIP)
- Representative from the Local Business Advisory Centre
- Representative from the Ghana Enterprise Agency
- Representative from the District Assembly

Participants will come across Ghana and virtual attendees from abroad will be included. Participants will be engaged through direct invitations to all stakeholders in Ghana.

Venue and other organisational aspects

hapaSpace, Kumasi. Kumasi is central to the locations of all the hubs that will be invited to participate in the programme as they move from across the country.

Training material to be used:

Power Point, Case Studies, Videos and Story boards. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda:

5 minutes	Technology Check <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sound check 	Gideon Brefo
5 min	Set-Up <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome & Introductions • Review of outcomes/purpose of the workshop 	Gideon Brefo
	Session 1 Title: From concept to planning and implementation	
5 min	Motivate Video about DIHs	Josiah K Eyison
10 min	House Keeping Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc	Josiah K Eyison
50 min	Topic 1: Defining Strategy	Josiah K Eyison
5 mins	Break	
50 min	Topic2: Strategic Planning	Josiah K Eyison
15 min	Group Activity Identifying project needs among those supported	Josiah K Eyison
15 min	Break	
15 min	Ice breaker: Contextualizing DIH needs	Josiah K Eyison
60 min	Topic 3: Strategy Formulation	Josiah K Eyison
	Session 2 Title: Strategy Development process	
20 min	Motivate: Brainstorming about strategy	Josiah K Eyison
45 min	Topic 1: Phase of the strategy process	Josiah K Eyison
5 min	Break	
60 min	Topic 2: Strategy Development Tools	Josiah K Eyison

15 min	Group Activity Group discussion: What is an ideal DIH?	Josiah K Eyison
15 min	Break	
10 min	Ice breaker Presentation of discussions	Josiah K Eyison
45 min	Topic 3: Build a strategy with different tools: SWOT analysis, Balanced Scorecard, PEST analysis	Josiah K Eyison
10 min	Wrap-Up Questions & answers	Josiah K Eyison
5 min	Workshop Closure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Closing Remarks and Evaluation Form Reminder 	Gideon Brefo

#5 Webinar: Purpose-driven DIH

June 2022

Organised online by ATBN, on June 2022

Webinar organisation and facilitation team:

Main moderator, facilitator, invited speakers and rapporteurs: TBC

Target groups / Participants:

60 participants will be targeted, representing stakeholders such as DIH Professionals, youth and women. By the end of this webinar, participants will be able to address purpose-driven innovation and manage change and growth opportunities.

Participants will be from any country, but 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations published through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects:

Online through Zoom or Teams and with the use of Google Jamboard

Training material to be used:

Power Point, Case Studies, Experts, Peer feedback, Live collaborative exercises

Draft Agenda:

The subchapter Purpose-driven Digital Innovation Hubs is composed of diverse themes, which will be delivered through different tools.

The first theme is the DIH itself in the sense that it is essential to define the identity and activity of the DIH to define a strategy. Therefore, the first contents covered are the purpose, the role and the processes of the DIH – setting the scene -, as well as key business challenges, project management and strategic planning – DIH activity. These contents will be addressed through one hands-on workshop in which participants will define their DIHs and outline an overall action plan addressing key challenges faced by African DIH based on the results of WP2.

After defining the purpose of the DIH, participants are invited to understand the purpose-driven innovation theme through a webinar addressing purpose-driven innovation, managing change and growth opportunities. These themes will be further complemented through additional materials upload on the project's website, not only focusing on DIH and purpose-driven innovation, but also focusing on the people's side – human-centred innovation.

#6 Masterclass: Gender-lens Finance-Bridging the gender finance gap July 2022

Organised online by ITC with the support of ATBN, YMH and PBS on 6 July 2022

Masterclass organization and facilitation team

Main Presenter/Trainer: ATBN, YMH, PBS: Gender-lens finance expert, gender-lens investor, a female entrepreneur with experience raising investment.

Facilitator (if needed): ATBN, YMH, PBS and ITC

Rapporteur: In the registration form, consent to record the session and take pictures should be included; the partner organizing and contributing to the masterclass will collect enough material for dissemination.

Target groups / Participants

25 participants are targeted for each masterclass; >50 will be reached, representing DIH managers and women entrepreneurs, as this masterclass focus on the gender-lens finance landscape (including stats and figures, how the sector has emerged, key actors and motivation) and offers a foundation in gender-lens investment - tools and approaches and explore the potential of capital in catalyzing gender equality and building inclusive innovation ecosystems.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organizational aspects:

Zoom; Google Jamboard or Mentimeter

Training material to be used:

PowerPoint presentations, case studies, gender-lens investment tools, e.g. Gender Integration Marker and 2X challenge criteria. These materials shall be prepared by the presenter and uploaded onto the AfriConEu online repository.

Draft Agenda:

Access to finance is one of the key challenges women entrepreneurs face, hindering the development of inclusive innovation ecosystems that can benefit society. In this masterclass, participants will understand the gender finance gap and how the gender-lens finance ecosystem is addressing them. They will get an introduction to the gender lens finance landscape and approaches and acquire tools to enable their DIHs to better support women entrepreneurs to access finance.

#7 Webinar Title: Gender lens innovation July 2022

Organised online by ATBN, on 13 July 2022

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator/ facilitator/ rapporteur: TBC

Invited speakers/trainers: Social innovators; experts in gender diversity; entrepreneurs/ entrepreneurship related professionals.

Target groups / Participants:

50 participants will be targeted, representing stakeholders such as DIH Professionals, youth and women. Participants will learn and understand women-led innovation opportunities and challenges. They will also acquire tools and methods for solutions design (products, services, programmes) around the specific needs of women, using women-centred design as an approach.

Participants will be from any country, but 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations published through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects:

Online through Zoom or Teams and with the use of Google Jamboard

Training material to be used:

Power Point, Case Studies, Videos, Polls

Draft Agenda:

In this subchapter, participants shall be introduced to gender lens thinking and tools. The goal is to help hub leaders build programs that contribute to promoting gender inclusion within their innovation ecosystem. Specifically, we will look at how to market programmes to the female audience, how to design programs around the unique needs of women and how to get access to relevant kinds of funding. Themes to be discussed include:

1) **Gender lens innovation – Building inclusive ecosystems:** Under this theme, participants will be guided first, to examine the drivers of gender inequality within their innovation ecosystems. Second, to understand how current structures and practices may contribute towards gender inequalities. And lastly, how these structures and practices can be challenged to promote gender inclusion. This theme will be delivered via a webinar.

2) **Gender lens Design – Designing inclusive programs:** Under this theme, participants will be introduced to gender-lens innovation including an introduction to human-centred design and applying a gender lens to human-centred design. This theme will be delivered as a hands on workshop in which participants will carry out a gender assessment of their own work in order to identify gender barriers as well as apply to knowledge acquired to design interventions and programmes that promote gender inclusion.

3) **Gender lens finance – Bridging the gender financing gap:** In this theme, participants will be introduced to the Gender Lens Investment landscape including key actors, emerging tools and approaches. They will also gain a deeper understanding of where the opportunities for gender lens investing lie and how to better support women entrepreneurs in their programmes to access funding. This theme will be delivered including talks by gender lens investors and experts.

#8 Webinar: DIH Business Model

July 2022

Organised online by ITC, on 20 July 2022

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator: tbc

Facilitators: Someone from ITC team or someone selected by them

Invited speakers/trainers: DIH business model specialist

Rapporteur: In the registration form, a specific field to give consent to record the session and take pictures is going to be included; the facilitator will make sure enough material is collected for dissemination

Target groups / Participants

50 participants will be targeted representing DIHs managers from both Africa (70%) and Europe. This webinar will aim to support DIHs in linking Strategy and Business Modelling, as business strategy and business model are two essential pre-conditions and fundamentals of any organization.

Participants will be engaged through open invitations published through the project website; social media as well as through direct invitations from partners contacts;

Venue and other organisational aspects

The webinar will be delivered through Zoom, while no interactive sessions are planned.

Training material to be used:

The material used will be mainly a PowerPoint presentation and case studies but additional material such as videos (ready to use training resources) may be used if the trainer considers them relevant. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda:

To be defined by the trainer. In general it will cover: introduction to business models and DIH services, Multi-sided business model and network effects, Case studies.

#9 Local Workshop: DIH Business Model**July 2022**

Organised as a HYBRID event in Kumasi by HAPA, on 14 July 2022

Workshop organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator: Gideon Brefo

Invited speakers/trainers: Dr. Gordon Adomdza: Design-Thinking, Innovation and Entrepreneurship are the three key words that resonate with Gordon. He is a Design Strategist who likes to connect with young people, startups, and corporations on one thing – how to bring about transformation. These key words provide a good idea of what his role entails: embrace of ambiguity in problem framing, empathetic ethnography, workshop facilitation, sensemaking data analysis, visualization, point of view construction, layered ideation, assumption mapping, minimum viable prototyping, value fulfilment architecture, business model value flows.

Rapporteur: Philipina B Appiah

Target groups / Participants

50 participants

- 2 members each from 23 DIHs
- Director of Programmes from the National Entrepreneurship and innovation Plan (NEIP)
- Representative from the Local Business Advisory Centre
- Representative from the Ghana Enterprise Agency
- Representative from the District Assembly

Participants will be from Ghana and also virtual attendees from abroad will be included.

Participants will be engaged through direct invitations to all stakeholders in Ghana.

Venue and other organisational aspects

hapaSpace, Kumasi. Kumasi is central to the locations of all the hubs that will be invited to participate in the programme as they move from across the country.

Training material to be used:

Power Point, Case Studies, Videos and Story boards. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda:

5 minutes	Technology Check • Sound check	Gideon Brefo
5 min	Set-Up Welcome & Introductions Review of outcomes/purpose of the workshop	Gideon Brefo
	Session 1 Title: Business models	
5 min	Motivate Video/ice breaker about business models	Gordon Adomdza
10 min	House Keeping Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc	Gordon Adomdza

50 min	<u>Topic 1: Linking Strategy and Business Modelling</u>	Gordon Adomdza
5 mins	<u>Break</u>	
50 min	<u>Topic2: Is the business model a part of the strategy?</u>	Gordon Adomdza
15 min	<u>Group Activity</u> Identifying project needs among those supported	Gordon Adomdza
15 min	<u>Break</u>	
15 min	<u>Ice breaker</u> Contextualizing DIH needs	Gordon Adomdza
60 min	<u>Topic 3: Understand the importance of business modelling for DIHs and the path to sustainability</u>	Gordon Adomdza
	<u>Session 2 A business model based on the offered service portfolio</u>	
20 min	<u>Motivate:</u> Brainstorming about strategy	Gordon Adomdza
45 min	<u>Topic 1: DIHs service and multi-actor approach</u>	Gordon Adomdza
5 min	<u>Break</u>	
60 min	<u>Topic 2: DIHs service and multi-actor approach</u>	Gordon Adomdza
15 min	<u>Group Activity</u> Group discussion: What is the multi-actor approach? Why should beneficiaries be involved in the design of DIH programs?	Gordon Adomdza
15 min	<u>Break</u>	
10 min	<u>Ice breaker</u> Presentation of discussions	Gordon Adomdza
45 min	<u>Topic 3: A business model based on the offered service portfolio</u>	Gordon Adomdza
10 min	<u>Wrap-Up</u> : Questions & answers	Gordon Adomdza
5 min	<u>Workshop Closure</u> Closing Remarks and Evaluation Form Reminder	Gideon Brefo

#10 Masterclass: Business strategy development for DIHs, lessons learnt October 2022

Organised online by ITC On 5 October 2022

Masterclass organisation and facilitation team

Main **Presenter/Trainer**: A business model and strategy specialist from ITC, with experience in working with DIHs

Facilitator (if needed): ITC team

Rapporteur: From ITC. Also, in the registration form, consent to record the session and take pictures should be included.

Target groups / Participants:

25 participants are targeted for each masterclass; >50 will be reached representing DIH managers. Participants of this masterclass will learn 10 steps to their business strategy, overview, trends and customer needs, competitor and technology, and the 4 pillars of business strategy. The second part

will focus on value proposition; how they can develop it through their services, define DIH's customer needs and demand, align with offered services, and improve.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects:

Zoom; Google Jamboard or Mentimeter

Training material to be used:

PowerPoint presentations, Examples from case studies, canvases for sustainable business models, best practice examples from DIH. The lecturer will prepare these materials and upload them onto the online repository of the project.

Draft Agenda:

Participants will learn key success factors for their business strategy, developing their DIH's value proposition through their services and customers' needs and demand. They will identify their organisation's core competencies and develop their mission and vision, which will be the base for defining DIHs value propositions.

Implementation Risks and Mitigation measures:

R: Availability of digital infrastructure; M: Record Session and host it online for future reference
R: Limited participation; M: Open registrations early and more widely

#11 Webinar: Collaborate to Innovate

July 2022

Organised online by ATBN, on July 2022

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main **moderator/ facilitator/ rapporteur:** TBC

Invited **speakers/trainers:** Community managers; stakeholder engagers; experts in co-creation processes; experts in open innovation

Target groups / Participants

50 participants will be targeted, representing stakeholders such as Local DIH Managers, Start-ups and Corporates. In this webinar participants will learn new organisational practices to manage innovation ecosystems, leveraging key stakeholders within innovation ecosystems (entrepreneurs, universities, risk capital providers, government, and large corporations) and engaging them in the most suitable way to enable their businesses to grow. Participants will be from any country, but 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations published through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Online through Zoom or Teams and with the use of Google Jamboard

Training material to be used:

Power Point, Case Studies, Videos, Polls

Draft Agenda:

In this webinar participants will learn new organisational practices to manage innovation ecosystems, leveraging key stakeholders within innovation ecosystems (entrepreneurs, universities, risk capital providers, government, and large corporations) and engaging them in the most suitable way to enable their businesses to grow.

#12 Webinar: The Business Model Navigator

October 2022

Organised online by ITC, on October 2022

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator: tbc

Facilitators: Someone from ITC team or someone selected by them

Invited speakers/trainers: DIH business model specialist

Rapporteur: In the registration form, a specific field to give consent to record the session and take pictures is going to be included; the facilitator will make sure enough material is collected for dissemination

Target groups / Participants

50 participants will be targeted representing DIHs managers from both Africa (70%) and Europe. This webinar aims to support DIHs in the development of a Business model which is appropriate for DIHs and encompasses their broad service portfolio.

Participants will be engaged through open invitations published through the project website; social media as well as through direct invitations from partners contacts.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom, No interactive sessions are planned

Training material to be used:

The material used will be mainly a PowerPoint presentation and case studies but additional material such as videos (ready to use training resources) may be used if the trainer considers them relevant. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda:

To be defined by the trainer. In general, it will include: Introduction to knowledge base and structure about business models and services for infrastructure, different business models.

#13 International Brokerage Event [Shared Opportunities]

October 2022

Organized hybrid by DP in BIG Bo, Bologna Italy, on 12-13 October 2022

Session/workshop organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator: An external moderator in an MC role would be ideal in order to provide continuity across the event and ensure smooth transitions between speakers. This role, depending on budget, would ideally be filled by an outside professional, such as a high-level speaker or journalist.

Facilitators: The overall event will require welcoming staff to handle registration and crowd control (approx. 4) Each round table and cycle of talks during day one will require a facilitator, likely drawn from speakers within that cycle. The interactive sessions on the second day will require facilitation, one per group within the session. These will likely be drawn from members of the consortium, depending on availability.

Invited speakers/trainers:

Round table participants (approximately 4 members each, with mixed profiles between investment, DIH and startup backgrounds)

Fintech; Agritech; Medtech; ICT4D.

Within the round tables and breakouts, there will be an effort to align topics and speakers with transversal themes connected to the AfriconEU project's topics:

- Towards a common digital market and connected startup ecosystem
- Digitalization, jobs for the 21st century and employment opportunities
- Business and investment opportunities in the African market
- Scouting digital entrepreneurs and startups in the African market

Possible costs for speaker fees/trainers, depending on finalized budget available will be considered.

Rapporteur: Particularly during the speaking sessions of the first day, professional support will be required for: Photography; Livestream/Remote Participation; Videography; Note taking/reporting
Photography and Videography will also be required during the second day, along with some potential remote participation, depending on format.

For the interactive sessions, the facilitators will be expected to support outputs from the tables and activities, with a second team member as a rapporteur for the session activities. These outputs will be particularly significant because they will be used to develop both matchmaking and speed dating in the latter part of the day, and feed into the design thinking bootcamps later in the project.

Target groups / Participants

Target of 200 participants, online and remote. Focus across 4 thematic subgroups: Startups; Investors; DIHs Managers; Other innovation supporters

Participants should be drawn in order to support a roughly even split between European and African ecosystems, with the intention to cover the strategic themes from the first day.

- Outreach strategies will leverage the networks of consortium members and the participants in the networking academy activities

- The participants from each event within the Networking Academy Program will need to be encouraged to join the brokerage event as a key element of the program.

- Outreach and registration will start within the end of April at the latest, beginning with direct invitations, leading into broader publicity and promotional efforts, and finally segueing into role-filling as initial responses come in.

Venue and other organisational aspects

BIG Bo offers a theatre with 110 seats (at full capacity), spaces for breakout rooms, workshops, bilateral meetings, and AV capacity appropriate to operating hybrid/remote events. Additional support for hybrid activities may be integrated based on final requirements.

Between the theatre, workshop area and overflow areas, it can support 200+ participants at full capacity; The space will require decoration such as rollup banners, cladding for the stage and similar, specifics TBD.

Registration, badging, etc. will be required on site, along with programs and similar hosting requirements.

Catering or offsite dinners will be provided during the event as needed.

Platform to manage the organization and booking of speed dating and matchmaking activities.

If possible, including sponsors as part of the event could provide the opportunity to expand the event, raise the profile of the onsite activities and provide focus to our work.

Training material to be used:

The presentational sessions for the first day will include material from each speaker/panel as needed. The interactive sessions for the second day will incorporate collaborative material such as question prompts and methodological structure.

Draft Agenda:

Remote Participation: The hubs within the AfriconEU Consortium may be mobilized as semi-independent events in parallel with the central event at Bologna. The remote events will combine local speakers (some of whom may be broadcast to the main event in Bologna) and livestreams of speakers from the event in Bologna. They can also mobilize their own interactive sessions on day two, contributing to the overall outputs of the activities. Throughout the event, but particularly on the second day, the remote sites will have access to the matchmaking and speed dating platforms joining bilateral meetings through an online platform such as Teams or Zoom.

Day 0:

- Setup and preparatory activities

Day 1:

The focus of Day 1 is presentational sessions. Each cycle will incorporate a round table with 4 speakers, followed by breakout sessions featuring the participants from that round table as either single speakers or in a dialogue/interview format.

Activities for the day:

- Final setup
- Welcoming, badging, organization
- Opening session
- Round table: Fintech
- Breakout sessions: Fintech
- Networking lunch
- Round table: Agritech
- Breakout sessions: Agritech
- Round table: Medtech
- Breakout sessions: Medtech
- Break
- Round table: ICT4D
- Breakout sessions: ICT4D
- Close day 1
- Brainstorming Buffet: Share ideas from the first day and opportunities for collaboration to prepare for the second day.

Day 2:

The focus of Day 2 will be on interactive sessions, designed to bring together participants and the speakers from Day 1.

The first part will focus on contextualizing the discussions from day 1, along

Activities for the day:

- Welcoming, badging, organization
- Opening session
- Short presentations on transversal themes, referencing day 1 sessions:
 - Towards a common digital market and connected startup ecosystem
 - Digitalization, jobs for the 21st century and employment opportunities
 - Business and investment opportunities in the African market
 - Scouting digital entrepreneurs and startups in the African market
- Networking lunch
- World café sessions: What collaborations are needed to deliver on the themes?
- World café presentations
- Speed dating, Worldcafe follow-ups and matchmaking breakouts, alongside adhoc speakers or artistic performances as needed
- Closing sessions

Expected outputs and KPIs

200 participants; 10 African DIHs representatives attending; 10 strategic partnerships between participants; 4 remote events at African partner DIHs; Video, photo, and feedback for use in subsequent communication and events; Material outputs from World Café sessions; X ideas and challenges to feed into design thinking bootcamps;

#14 Webinar: Durable Funding Sources for DIHs

October 2022

Organised online by ATBN, on October 2022

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Moderator/ Facilitator/ Rapporteur: TBC

Invited speakers/trainers: Expert on DIH management/experienced manager or researcher working on DIHs.

Target groups / Participants

50 participants will be targeted representing Local DIH Managers, Investors, Youth and Start-ups. This webinar is intended to provide participants with information on best practices surrounding durable funding sources and revenue streams for DIHs. By the end of the webinar, participants will be able to identify the business model and funding/revenue streams for their DIH, along with potential alternatives or added sources.

Participants will be from any country, but 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations published through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom; Google Jamboard

Training material to be used:

Power Point and case studies

Draft Agenda:

This webinar will focus on potential revenue models for digital innovation hubs. The emphasis will be placed on services the hubs can offer as platforms, such as providing space for events and operations, training programs for professionals and aspiring professionals, and consulting and matchmaking services for early-stage projects. It will also look into sponsorship and partnerships available to DIHs such as working with MNCs as training centres, working with financial actors to support incubation and acceleration programs, and ongoing relationships with groups such as chambers of commerce, civil society groups, or government entities. Alternative uses for the space, such as providing retail space, rental of equipment, sale of alternative services and other potential revenue streams will be incorporated into the discussion.

Implementation Risks and Mitigation measures

R: Availability of digital infrastructure; M: Record Session and host it online for future reference

R: Limited participation; M: Open registrations early and more widely

#15 Masterclass: Essentials of innovation finance

October 2022

Organised online by ITC with the help of DP, on 26 October 2022

Masterclass organisation and facilitation team

Main Presenter/Trainer: A presenter from DP with a thorough command of innovation financing, potentially having worked as a CFO within a start-up, with an M&A or VC firm, or in an advisory role with an incubator or accelerator. A university professor may also be appropriate, though ideally with hands-on experience.

Facilitator (if needed): From DP and ITC

Rapporteur: In the registration form, consent to record the session and take pictures should be included; the partner organising and contributing to the masterclass will collect enough material for dissemination.

Target groups / Participants

25 participants are targeted for each masterclass; >50 will be reached representing DIH managers, DIH financial managers, DIH project managers, as this masterclass will be an overview of the key elements in innovation finance, key innovation financing terms, matching projects with relevant funding sources and support them in developing a financial plan, mapping the fundamental sources of finance within an ecosystem and identifying what will be needed to access them.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom; Google Jamboard or Mentimeter

Training material to be used

Powerpoints, Case Studies, Canvases and Realia (such as term sheets and financial documents from genuine investments). Participants will be asked to fill in and reflect on some materials during the masterclass.

Draft Agenda

The main areas covered will include the role played by financing and funding in innovative projects. There will be an overview of traditional financing, alongside an introduction to alternative financing methods. Alongside the various financing options available to innovative projects, a few fundamentals of accessing them will be introduced.

#16 Webinar: Phases of Investment

October 2022

Organised online by ATBN, on October 2022

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Moderator/ Facilitator/ Rapporteur: TBC

Invited speakers/trainers: Finance expert, preferably with hands-on experience in innovation finance/investments

Target groups / Participants

50 participants will be targeted representing Local DIH Managers, Investors, Youth and Start-ups. This webinar is intended to provide participants with information on best practices surrounding durable funding sources and revenue streams for DIHs. By the end of the webinar, participants will be able to identify the business model and funding/revenue streams for their DIH, along with potential alternatives or added sources.

This webinar is meant as a train the trainers' program designed to support DIH staff in advising projects and creating programs to support innovation financing. Participants will be able to define the key phases of investment over a project lifecycle, along with typical features of those phases, and create or guide the creation of a financing plan for an innovative project.

Participants will be from any country, but 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations published through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom

Training material to be used

Power Point

Draft Agenda

This webinar will cover the core phases of traditional investment. This will include pre-seed, seed funding, series A, B and C funding, where those funding streams commonly fall within the lifecycle of an innovative project and how they are commonly used. It will also cover some of the common relationships developed during the investment process, such as grants, debt and equity, and also the processes of incubation and acceleration that often accompany equity and investment relationships. It will finally analyze some of the common types of investors, such as FFF, venture capital, VC funds, corporate VC, angel investors, banks, open innovation, and others. The role, value and risks of international funding and diaspora networks, along with series entrepreneurs and reinvestment should be discussed as well.

#17 Webinar: Building a Business Plan

November 2022

Organised online by ITC, on 16 November 2022

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator/ facilitator: tbc

Invited speakers/trainers: DIH business plan specialist

Rapporteur: In the registration form, a specific field to give consent to record the session and take pictures is going to be included; the facilitator will make sure enough material is collected for dissemination

Target groups / Participants

50 participants will be targeted (target: 15 participants). These will be DIHs managers from Africa, with the aim to train them on the use of different business planning tools.

An open invitation call will be promoted through the project website and social media; direct invitations will be sent through AfriConEU partner contacts.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom, Mentimeter/ Jamboard, Breakout rooms

Training material to be used

The material used will be mainly a PowerPoint presentation but additional material such as videos and case studies (ready to use training resources) may be used if the trainer considers them relevant. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda

To be defined by the trainer. In general, it will cover the following topics: DIH & Business plan, Importance of Business plan, Building Business Plan tools – holistic overview of a business plan for the development of DIH, which will support a more focused and efficient hub development process.

#18 Local Workshop: Draft a Preliminary Business Model for your DIHs

November 2022

Organised as a HYBRID event in Kumasi by HAPA, in November 2022

Workshop organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator: *Gideon Brefo*

Invited speakers/trainers: Dr. Gordon Adomdza

Rapporteur: Philipina B Appiah

Target groups / Participants

50 participants

- 2 members each from 23 DIHs
- Director of Programmes from the National Entrepreneurship and innovation Plan (NEIP)
- Representative from the Local Business Advisory Centre
- Representative from the Ghana Enterprise Agency
- Representative from the District Assembly

Participants will be from Ghana and also virtual attendees from abroad will be included.

Participants will be engaged through direct invitations to all stakeholders in Ghana.

Venue and other organisational aspects

hapaSpace, Kumasi. Kumasi is central to the locations of all the hubs that will be invited to participate in the programme as they move from across the country.

Training material to be used

Power Point, Case Studies, Videos and Story boards. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda		
5 min	Technology Check • Sound check	Gideon Brefo
5 min	Set-Up • Welcome & Introductions • Review of outcomes/purpose of the workshop	Gideon Brefo
	Session 1 Title: Business Model Canvas	
5 min	Motivate Video/ice breaker about business models	Gordon Adomdza
10 min	House Keeping Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc	Gordon Adomdza
50 min	• Topic 1: BMC for DIHs	Gordon Adomdza
5 mins	Break	
50 min	• Topic2: Step by step guide to developing a BMC	Gordon Adomdza
15 min	Group Activity Draw a BMC for your DIH with the template given	Gordon Adomdza
15 min	Break	
15 min	Ice breaker Contextualizing DIH needs	Gordon Adomdza
60 min	• Topic 3: The Various Business Model	Gordon Adomdza
	Session 2: Lean Canvas	
20 min	Motivate Brainstorming about strategy	Gordon Adomdza
45 min	Topic 1: The Lean Business Model	Gordon Adomdza
5 min	Break	
60 min	Topic 2: Step by step guide to LBMC	Gordon Adomdza
15 min	Group Activity Group discussion: Why use the lean business model	Gordon Adomdza
15 min	Break	
10 min	Ice breaker Presentation of discussions	Gordon Adomdza
45 min	Topic 3: Convert the BMC drawn in the earlier activity into a lean canvas	Gordon Adomdza
10 min	Wrap-Up: Questions & answers	Gordon Adomdza
5 min	Workshop Closure • Closing Remarks and Evaluation Form Reminder	Gideon Brefo

#19 Local Workshop: Bootstrapping, revenue models and managerial accounting (*Designing an accelerator*)

December 2022

Organised as a HYBRID event in Kampala (Uganda) by Outbox, in December 2022

Workshop organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator: Ivan Mandela (SHONA Uganda)

Ivan is a co-founder and Director of investment at SHONA. SHONA is a business advisory and SME training firm that helps SMEs grow revenues and become profitable businesses.

Over the last ten years, Ivan has been instrumental in providing investment readiness support to SMEs in Uganda. He has supported over 30 SMEs to collectively raise \$15M in capital through his

relationships with Venture capitalists and VC funds. Ivan is on the investment committee of Finca Ventures where he is involved in advising the selection process of potential investees.

Invited speakers/trainers: The following speakers will be invited to the event:

- Bob Ogwang will support with the online training facilitation
- Joseph Ocailap will support with the online training facilitation

Rapporteur: [Perez Masinde](#) : Rapporteur to undertake the note taking exercise

Target groups / Participants

- Two members from each of the Digital Innovation hubs under AfriconEU
 - Digital Innovation Hubs in Uganda (Start-up Uganda association and others): Approx 13 members will attend from mid-level management or investment analysts from members
- The initiative will target to host up-to 50 participants.

Venue and other organisational aspects

The event will be hosted at Outbox offices. Virtual participants will use Zoom for participation

Training material to be used

- Mural for the online audience
- Whiteboards, flipcharts for the in-person engagement
- Slack channel for conversations

Draft Agenda

Time	Content/Process	Who
<i>Before the event</i>		
1 month to training	Self-assessment of potential attendees on their capacity to support startups on revenue models and managerial accounting	Ivan Mandela
2 weeks to training	Pre-reading material on revenue models and managerial account	Ivan Mandela
1 week to training	Pre-training case study assignment on the workshop	Ivan Mandela
<i>Training day</i>		
9:00 (20 minutes)	Welcome and introductions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participants online and in-person - Housekeeping instruction - Overview of the AfriconEU initiative - Focus of the training 	Perez Masinde
9.20 (20 minutes)	Introduction to revenue models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview of revenue models - Revenue models for start-ups in various sectors 	Ivan Mandela
9.40 (50 minutes)	Group discussion on revenue models based on pre-reading case study	Ivan Mandela
10.30 (30 minutes)	Break	
11.00 (30 minutes)	Introduction to managerial accounting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Balance sheet, income statement and cash flow statement - Unit economics for businesses 	Ivan Mandela
11.30 1 hour	Group discussion based on case study: Constructing your income and cash flow statement	
12.30	Debrief and wrap-up	Ivan Mandela // Perez Masinde

#20 Webinar: Crowdfunding and Microcredit

December 2022

Organised online by ATBN with the support of DP, on December 2022

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator/ facilitator/ rapporteur: TBC

Invited speakers/trainers: Crowdfunding expert or entrepreneur with crowdfunding experience, possibly co-taught with a representative from a microcredit institution.

Target groups / Participants

50 participants will be targeted representing local DIH Managers and Start-ups. This webinar will introduce participants to crowdfunding and microcredit as innovation financing sources. This will be primarily in the context of the trainers' efforts but will incorporate some options that may apply to the funding of DIHs as well. By the end, the participants will have the knowledge to advise and support projects as they consider, plan, and execute crowdfunding or microcredit campaigns. Participants will be from any country, but 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations published through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom, Google Jamboard

Training material to be used

Power Point and Best Practice

Draft Agenda

This webinar will cover two emerging funding sources. It will address the benefits and drawbacks of crowdfunding both in equity and non-equity forms and provide some initial guidance as to the demands and requirements of running a crowdfunding campaign. It will also address the key features and demands related to the emerging microcredit movement, both in terms of formal lending partners and peer to peer engagements. The mechanical elements of these funding sources will be addressed, along with their common uses, how they correlate with other funding sources and how projects can position themselves to take advantage of these sources.

#21 Webinar: Impact Investing and Subsidized Finance

December 2022

Organised online by ATBN with the support of DP, on December 2022

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator/ facilitator/ rapporteur: TBC

Invited speakers/trainers: Social innovation/entrepreneurship expert, preferably with public sector experience.

Target groups / Participants

40 participants will be targeted representing local DIH Managers, Investors, Youth, Start-ups. The webinar will cover the fundamentals of impact investing and subsidized finance, what the funders are looking for, how they operate and where they can fall within the lifecycle of innovation finance. Following that, there will be a discussion of key elements of impact tracking and planning, vision and mission statements, theory of change, balanced scorecards, and triple bottom line tracking. These tools will be contextualized in terms of how to present them to impact investors or in applications for subsidized funding.

Participants will be from any country, but 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations published through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects
Zoom, Google Jamboard
Training material to be used
PowerPoint presentations, canvases/fillable forms for vision and mission statement and, impact tracking tools.
Draft Agenda
This webinar will present the basics of impact investing and subsidized finance, such as grant funding from public entities or non-profits. These financing sources will be presented in the context of overall innovation financing including their common uses. In particular, there will be a discussion of the requirements of those pursuing such financing, notably impact metrics and tools such as vision and mission statements, theory of change, balanced scorecards and other resources that can help provide evidence of triple bottom line impact which can support the pursuit of impact investing and subsidized finance.

2023

#22 Local Workshop: Building and Using a Network of Funding Sources January 2023

Organised as a HYBRID event in Akure, Nigeria by ECA, on January 2023

Workshop organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator: Nwanne from [ECA], who has the appropriate experience for hosting and moderating events.

Facilitators: Members of ECA.

Invited speakers/trainers: TBD

Rapporteur: Husseinat [ECA], will be responsible for documentation of the event. She will be responsible for written workshop's minutes, voice recorder, testimonies from participants etc. A photographer may be contracted for the visual documentation.

Target groups / Participants

As the workshop's aim is to distribute knowledge on the best technology transfer processes, the participants to be invited include representatives from academia and the private sector including DIH managers and start-ups. Government representatives will also be invited.

In order to participate, invitees should have experience with DIHs and an open mind to learn and teach others what they know of the topics to be discussed.

Most of the participant's organization operate within Africa- Nigeria specifically Akure, Lagos, Abuja. (Online participants can operate from anywhere in the world).

The regular mode of communication will be used to bring the participants on board.

- calls to speakers,
- emails to stakeholders already involved,
- direct invitations to hubs/ businesses/universities,
- local and online media to gather attention from members of the general public like students that may be interested.

Venue and other organisational aspects

The Venue is the Dome, an international cultural centre offering the required equipment and digital infrastructure.

Training material to be used

PowerPoint presentations; Canvases and similar forms; Best practical examples.

Draft Agenda

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Session 1 Title: The Funding Landscape		
Motivate	10	Ice breaker
House Keeping	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc.
Topic 1: Innovation lifecycles	45	Delivery will involve a breakout session where participants will go into their preferred groups to discuss the topics simultaneously. Online participants will participate in default topic group that the livestreaming camera is stationed with.
Topic 2: Funding sources and needs over an innovation lifecycle		
Topic 3: What is innovation ecosystem? How do you map it?		
Feedback	15	Presentation of discussions
Group Activity	15	Identifying project needs among those supported and contextualizing project needs
Break	15	
Session 2 Title: DIHs as a Reference Point		
Welcome Back	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc.
Topic 1: Varied needs of funding sources	45	Delivery will involve a breakout session where participants will go into their preferred groups to discuss the topics simultaneously. Online participants will participate in default topic group that the livestreaming camera is stationed with.
Topic 2: Roles played by DIHs between financing & projects, examples best practices		
Topic 3: How various activities are funded, examples, best practices		
Feedback	15	Presentation of discussions
Group Activity	15	Group discussion: Project ideas for participant hubs

#23 Local Workshop: Preparing projects for investment and investor readiness (*Designing an accelerator*)

January 2023

Organised as a HYBRID event in Kampala (Uganda) by Outbox, in January 2023

Workshop organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator: Ivan Mandela (SHONA Uganda)

Ivan is a co-founder and Director of investment at SHONA. SHONA is a business advisory and SME training firm that helps SMEs grow revenues and become profitable businesses.

Over the last ten years, Ivan has been instrumental in providing investment readiness support to SMEs in Uganda. He has supported over 30 SMEs to collectively raise \$15M in capital through his relationships with Venture capitalists and VC funds. Ivan is on the investment committee of Finca Ventures where he is involved in advising the selection process of potential investees.

Invited speakers/trainers: The following speakers will be invited to the event:

- **Rebecca Mincy** is the Director at the Acumen Resilient Agriculture Fund. She has previously managed Acumen's portfolio of Agricultural businesses in East Africa.
- Bob Ogwang will support with the online training facilitation

- Joseph Ocailap will support with the online training facilitation

Rapporteur: [Perez Masinde](#) : Rapporteur to undertake the note taking exercise

Target groups / Participants

- Two members from each of the Digital Innovation hubs under AfriconEU
 - Digital Innovation Hubs in Uganda (Start-up Uganda association and others): Approx 13 members will attend from mid-level management or investment analysts from members
- The initiative will target to host up-to 50 participants.

Venue and other organisational aspects

The event will be hosted at Outbox offices. Virtual participants will use Zoom for participation.

Training material to be used

- Mural for the online audience
- Whiteboards, flipcharts for the in-person engagement
- Slack channel for conversations

Draft Agenda

Time	Content/Process	Who
<i>Before the event</i>		
1 month to training	Self-assessment of potential attendees on their capacity to support start-ups with investment readiness	Ivan Mandela
2 weeks to training	Pre-reading material on corporate finance and business valuation	Ivan Mandela
1 week to training	Pre-training case study assignment on the workshop	Ivan Mandela
<i>Training day</i>		
9:00 (20 minutes)	Welcome and introductions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participants online and in-person - Housekeeping instruction - Overview of the AfriconEU initiative - Focus of the training 	Perez Masinde
9.50 (50 minutes)	Introduction to Corporate Finance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview of investment landscape (PE/VC) within the African context - Understanding the investment process 	Ivan Mandela
10.00 (30 minutes)	How Acumen capital undertakes its due diligence process for potential investments	Rebecca Mincy
10.30 (30 minutes)	Break	
11.00 (1 hour)	Group assignment based on case study	Ivan Mandela
12.30 30 minutes	Debrief and wrap-up	Ivan Mandela
12.30	Debrief and wrap-up	Ivan Mandela // Perez Masinde

#24 Webinar: Valuations of Projects, Financial Management, Projections January 2023

Organised online by ATBN with the support of DP, on January 2023

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator/ facilitator/ rapporteur: TBC

Invited speakers/trainers: Experienced financial professional; university lecturer

Target groups / Participants

40 participants will be targeted representing Local DIH Managers, Investors, Youth, Start-ups. The webinar will include the key uses of business metrics and KPIs as management tools along with examples of good metrics and best practices. In particular, there will be an emphasis on SMART metrics and impact evaluation. Following these elements, there will be a discussion of how to make justifiable projections based on current metrics, and how to perform valuations of startups.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom, Google Jamboard

Training material to be used

Presentation, extensive handouts especially including any presented formulas or other complex tools should be provided.

Draft Agenda

This webinar will cover the main valuation methods for innovative projects, such as discounted cash flow, scorecards, and benchmarking. It will also look at the primary aspects of financial reporting, including key metrics regarding income and cash flow, market size, growth rates and so on. Non-financial metrics will also be included, especially in the context of impact metrics as covered in other modules. Notably, in the context of good management, SMART metrics and KPI settings will also be addressed. Justifiable bases for projections of all of the above in the absence of available data will also be covered.

#25 Webinar: Leverage start-up creation from innovative technologies January 2023

Organised online by PBS, in January 2023

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator/ facilitator: Someone from PBS team or someone selected by them

Invited speakers/trainers: Mário Alves, Maria Oliveira, Maria Isabel Franco (tbc)

Rapporteur: From PBS. In the registration form, a specific field to give consent to record the session and take pictures is going to be included.

Target groups / Participants

50 participants will be targeted representing DIHs managers and start-ups from Africa and Europe. The main objective of this webinar is for participants to understand the specificities of a technology-based start-up, and to comprehend the entrepreneurial journey that should be followed to address them.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom; Mentimeter/ Jamboard; Breakout rooms

Training material to be used

The material used will be mainly a PowerPoint presentation but additional material such as videos and case studies (ready to use training resources) may be used if the trainer considers them relevant. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda

To be defined by the trainer. This webinar focuses on the creation of start-ups technology-based, addressing the entrepreneurial journey from ideation to scale.

#26 Masterclass: Financing Digital Innovation Hubs

January 2023

Organised online by ITC with the help of DP, on 11 January 2023

Masterclass organisation and facilitation team

Main Presenter/Trainer: An expert from DP who have worked with a DIH and meta-level, analysing DIHs or managing a network. That is advantageous if they have experience doing so within the African context.

Facilitator (if needed): from DP and ITC

Rapporteur: From ITC. In the registration form, consent to record the session and take pictures should be included.

Target groups / Participants

25 participants are targeted for each masterclass; >50 will be reached representing DIH managers, and DIH financial managers, as this masterclass will cover funding models and revenue streams for DIH management, sources of subsidised finance, impact investing, bootstrapping, fundamentals of managerial accounting and developing a network or ecosystem of financing sources.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom; Google Jamboard or Mentimeter

Training material to be used

PowerPoint presentations. Canvases. Best practices and case studies. Material such as the Creative Hubkit or content from Afrilabs, which can be applied outside the masterclass as guidebooks.

Participants, especially those who have engaged with other elements of the academy program, will be encouraged to bring in and present their own stories, engaging with their specific circumstances as part of the course program.

Draft Agenda

Participants will end the masterclass with the resources and information needed to deliver a concrete financial model for their DIH. This will incorporate the processes of limiting operational costs, developing revenue streams, identifying funding sources, and maintaining a network of critical actors within the ecosystem.

#27 Masterclass Title: Lessons from European start-ups

January 2023

Organised online by PBS on 1 February January 2023

Masterclass organisation and facilitation team

Main Presenter/Trainer: From PBS: Entrepreneurship experts; start-up creation experts; sustainable development experts; business strategy experts; innovation managers

Facilitator (if needed): PBS and ITC

Rapporteur: In the registration form, consent to record the session and take pictures should be included; the partner organising and contributing to the masterclass will ensure enough material is collected for dissemination.

Target groups / Participants

25 participants are targeted for each masterclass; >50 will be reached representing DIH and start-up managers. Participants of this masterclass will learn key success factors of European start-ups to take the African start-up economy to the next level.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website, social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom; Google Jamboard or Mentimeter

Training material to be used

PowerPoint presentations, polls, additional materials. The lecturer will prepare these materials and upload them onto the online repository.

Draft Agenda

By introducing fundamental subjects such as access to talent, finance and public policy aspects (insights for data-driven policymaking) that drove Europe into a unified market, African DIHs and start-ups will acquire insights significant towards start-up growth and development of a common market. European start-ups are indeed being created and growing at an unprecedented pace, attracting the attention of global investors, customers, and corporate partners alike so that several lessons could be exploited. The ultimate goal is to build a community of innovators between Europe and Africa and understand how collaborations could be fostered.

#28 Masterclass Title: Building a Theory of Change

February 2023

Organised online by Stimmuli with the help of ITC on February 2023

Masterclass organization and facilitation team

Main Presenter/Trainer: From Stimmuli; Also, an invited trainers with expertise in impact strategy and management, Theory of change experience.

Facilitator (if needed): From Stimmuli

Rapporteur: In the registration form, consent to record the session and take pictures should be included; the partner organizing and contributing to the masterclass will collect enough material for dissemination.

Target groups / Participants

25 participants are targeted for each masterclass; >50 will be reached representing DIH managers, investors, policy-makers, as this masterclass offer participants a unique opportunity to learn tools and apply impact management and measurement. It will provide a deep dive into the Theory of change approach to monitoring impact.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organizational aspects

Zoom; Google Jamboard or Mentimeter

Training material to be used

PowerPoint presentations, case studies, impact measurement tools and methodologies, e.g. Theory of Change. These materials shall be prepared by the presenter and uploaded onto an online repository.

Draft Agenda

Every business, program, or initiative impacts (positive or negative). Knowing how to measure this impact allows managers, investors, policy-makers, and implementers to make informed and better decisions to enhance and strengthen programs that improve lives or modify or reassign resources of those programs that are not achieving their objectives.

#29 Webinar: Impact Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning February 2023

Organised online by ATBN, in February 2023

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main **moderator/facilitator/ rapporteur**: TBC

Invited **speakers/trainers**: Impact evaluation expert

Target groups / Participants

50 participants will be targeted representing DIH leads, Professionals, youth and women. The webinar will provide to the participants an introduction to MEL (Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning) frameworks. It will enable participants to understand impact language, be exposed to practical tools in the field, and contribute to hubs ability to better report on their impact.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom; Google Jamboard

Training material to be used

Videos; Case studies; PowerPoint presentations; Polls

Draft Agenda

The main objective of this webinar is to provide to the participants an introduction to MEL (Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning) frameworks. Several learning outcomes can be pointed out such as understanding impact language, being exposed to practical tools in the field and contributing to hubs ability to better report on their impact.

#30 Local Workshop: Gender Lens Innovation February 2023

Organised as a HYBRID event by BUNI, in February 2023

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Moderator/facilitator: BUNI

Speakers/trainers: TBC

Rapporteur: BUNI

Target groups / Participants

More than 15 participants will be targeted, representing DIH, startups, innovators, ICT professionals, SME, local governments, among others.

Venue and other organisational aspects

TBC (BUNI space, Zoom...)

Training material to be used

Seminar-style presentations; Group discussions; Hands-on work; Take home tasks to complete before/ after the workshop; Case studies; Work in groups.

Draft Agenda

In this workshop, participants shall be introduced to gender lens thinking and tools. The goal of the webinar is to help hub leaders build programs that contribute to the decrease in gender inequality. Specifically, we will look at how to market programmes to the female audience, how to design programs around the unique needs of women and how to get access to relevant kinds of funding. Topics to be discussed: (i) Marketing with a gender lens; (ii) Gender lens Design; (iii) Gender lens finance.

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Workshop Title: Gender Lens Innovation		
Motivate	5	Video/ice breaker
House Keeping	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: Marketing with a gender lens (What is a gender lens approach and how is it relevant to marketing?)	50	Lecture/brainstorm/activity/ individual task/ presentation, etc
Break	15	
Topic 2: Gender-lens design (Intro to human-centred design, including social entrepreneurs' definition; as well as add a gender lens to human-centred design)	50	Lecture/brainstorm/activity/ individual task/ presentation, etc
Learning Activity: What is Gender-lens design?	20	Brainstorming & Presentation
Break	30	
Topic 3: Gender-lens finance (Intro to Gender Len Investment - Goals, history, the need, basic concepts, example of funds)	40	Lecture/brainstorm/activity/ individual task/ presentation, etc
Learning Activity: Where are the opportunities for gender lens investing in women's financial inclusion?	20	Brainstorming & Presentation
Total Time for Workshop	240	4h (for example, a whole morning)

#31 Webinar: Data-driven innovation

March 2023

Organised online by PBS, in March 2023

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main **moderator/facilitator**: TPD - Someone from PBS team or someone selected by them

Invited **speakers/trainers**: Pedro Amorim; Bernardo Almada Lobo (tbc)

Rapporteur: From PBS. Also, in the registration form, a specific field to give consent to record the session and take pictures is going to be included;

Target groups / Participants

50 participants will be targeted (target 15 participants) representing DIHs managers and startups from Africa. This webinar addresses the increasing role of data and data analytics, highlighting, in particular, the potential of data-driven innovation (DDI) for businesses to grow.

Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom; Mentimeter/ Jamboard; Breakout rooms

Training material to be used

The material used will be mainly a PowerPoint presentation but additional material such as videos and case studies (ready to use training resources) may be used if the trainer considers them relevant. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda

In this webinar participants will learn the key drivers of data-driven innovation (DDI), which are related to i) data generation and collection, ii) data processing and analysis, and iii) data-driven decision making.

#32 Local Workshop: The Technology Transfer Process

March 2023

Organised as a HYBRID event in Kumasi by ECA, on March 2023

Workshop organisation and facilitation team

Main **moderator**: Nwanne [ECA]

Facilitators: The ECA team will be responsible for the logistics of the event.

Invited **speakers/trainers**: TBD

Rapporteur: Husseinat [ECA] will be responsible for documentation of the event. She will be responsible for written workshop's minutes, maybe voice recorder, testimonies from participants etc. A photographer may be contracted for the visual documentation.

Target groups / Participants

As the workshop's aim is to distribute knowledge on the best technology transfer processes, the participants to be invited include representatives from academia and the private sector including DIH managers and start-ups. Government representatives will also be invited. In order to participate, invitees should have experience with DIHs and an open mind to learn and teach others what they know of the topics to be discussed.

Most of the participant's organization operate within Africa- Nigeria specifically Akure, Lagos, Abuja. (Online participants can operate from anywhere in the world).

The regular mode of communication will be used to bring the participants on board: calls to speakers; email invitation to stakeholders, direct invitations to hubs/ businesses/universities, ; local and online media to gather attention from members of the general public like students that may be interested.

Venue and other organisational aspects

The Dome

Training material to be used

PowerPoint presentations; case studies; Canvases for technology transfer; Best practical examples from DIH

Draft Agenda

The workshop will cover topics such as the technology transfer concept and process; its benefits and characteristics; the legal framework and technology transfer offices etc.

#33 Webinar: Business Intelligence and Analytics

April 2023

Organised online by PBS, in April 2023

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator/facilitator: TBD - Someone from PBS team or someone selected by them

Invited speakers/trainers: Carlos Soares; Bruno Silva (tbc)

Rapporteur: From PBS; In the registration form, a specific field to give consent to record the session and take pictures is going to be included;

Target groups / Participants

50 participants (target 15 participants) representing DIHs managers and startups from Africa and Europe. During this webinar, participants will acquire or refresh skills in the area of data science and engineering, as well as understand how to bridge the gap between technology and business management.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom; Mentimeter/ Jamboard; Breakout rooms

Training material to be used

The material used will be mainly a PowerPoint presentation but additional material such as videos and case studies (ready to use training resources) may be used if the trainer considers them relevant. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda

To be defined by the trainer

This webinar combines management and technological skills, addressing themes like data mining, data analytics, quality of data, management systems, business intelligence, among others.

Implementation Risks and Mitigation measures

R: Availability of digital infrastructure; M: Record Session and host it online for future reference

R: Limited participation; M: Open registrations early and more widely

#34 Masterclass: Business Intelligence and Analytics

April 2023

Organised online by PBS on 12 April 2023

Masterclass organisation and facilitation team

Main Presenter/Trainer: From PBS: Data Mining professionals; Business Intelligence experts; data science professionals.

Facilitator (if needed): From PBS and ITC

Rapporteur: From PBS; In the registration form, consent to record the session and take pictures should be included;

Target groups / Participants

25 participants are targeted for each masterclass; >50 will be reached representing DIH managers and data analytics in DIHs, as this masterclass combines management and technological skills, addressing themes like data mining, data analytics, data quality, management systems, and business intelligence.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website, social media and newsletters. Also, through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom; Google Jamboard or Mentimeter

Training material to be used

PowerPoint presentations, polls, additional materials. The lecturer will prepare these materials and upload them onto the online repository.

Draft Agenda

During this masterclass, participants will acquire or refresh their data science and engineering skills and understand the latest transformations in business intelligence and data analytics, bridging the gap between technology and business management.

#35 Local Workshop: The Technology Valorisation Process

April 2023

Organised as a HYBRID event by BUNI, in April 2023

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Moderator/facilitator: BUNI; **Speakers/trainers:** TBC; **Rapporteur:** BUNI

Target groups / Participants

More than 15 participants will be targeted, representing DIH, startups, innovators, ICT professionals, SME, local governments, among others.

Venue and other organisational aspects

TBC

Training material to be used

Seminar-style presentations; Group discussions; Hands-on work: Technology Assessment Dashboard; Case studies; The Technology Transfer Canvas, etc.; Take home tasks to complete before/ after the workshop.

Draft Agenda

This workshop builds on the concept of technology transfer discussed in workshop 4. It focuses on the technology transfer process with emphasis on value proposition, market analysis, the capacity of the research team and the partners involved. It also highlights the relevance of the time of market entry and adhering to a strong strategic plan, patenting and proof of concept.

Topics to be discussed: The technology identification phase; Results of R&D activity; Invention disclosure; (iv) The technology assessment phase; Factors to make the right decisions; The value proposition of the technology; Market analysis; Time of market entry; Protection strength; The capacity of the research team; Pathways to transfer technology; Partners in technology transfer; Technology transfer strategic plan; Market validation; The technology protection phase; Overview of intellectual property rights; Getting the technology protected by patenting; The patenting process in a nutshell; The technology readiness phase; Bridging the gap towards the market; Development and proof of concept.

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Workshop Title: The Technology Valorisation Process		
Motivate	5	Ice breaker
House Keeping	5	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: The technology identification phase	10	Delivery will include seminar-style presentation; group discussions; hands-on work, etc.)
Topic 2: Results of R&D activity	10	
Topic 3: Invention disclosure	10	
Topic 4: The technology assessment phase	10	
Topic 5: Factors to make the right decisions	10	
Topic 6: The value proposition of the technology	10	
Topic 7: Market analysis	10	
Topic 8: Time of market entry	10	
Topic 9: Protection strength	10	
Topic 10: Capacity of the research team	10	
Break	20	
Topic 11: Pathways to transfer technology	10	Delivery will include seminar-style presentation; group discussions; hands-on work, etc.)
Topic 12: Partners in technology transfer	10	
Topic 13: Technology transfer strategic plan	10	
Topic 14: Market validation	10	
Topic 15: The technology protection phase	10	
Topic 16: Overview of intellectual property rights	10	
Topic 17: Getting the technology protected by patenting	10	
Topic 18: The patenting process in a nutshell	10	
Topic 19: The technology readiness phase	10	
Topic 20: Bridging the gap towards the market	10	

Topic 21: Development and proof of concept	10	
Total Time for the workshop	240	4 hours (for example a whole morning)

#36 Webinar: Fast-tracking technologies to market May 2023

Organised online by PBS, in May 2023

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator: There is a need for an external moderator with specific expertise in the topic. Profile: Experts in the creation of value from knowledge through technology, entrepreneurship and/or open innovation; experts in technology commercialisation.

Facilitators: Someone from PBS team or someone selected by them

Invited speakers/trainers: Rui Serapicos (tbc)

Rapporteur: From PBS; In the registration form, a specific field to give consent to record the session and take pictures is going to be included.

Target groups / Participants

50 participants invited; (target 15 participants) representing DIHs managers and startups from Africa and Europe. This webinar will promote the identification of new applications for technology with high added value or new market segments for a product or service, increasing the profitability of the business.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom; Mentimeter/ Jamboard; Breakout rooms

Training material to be used

The material used will be mainly a PowerPoint presentation but additional material such as videos and case studies (ready to use training resources) may be used if the trainer considers them relevant. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda

TBD; This webinar examines the mechanisms through which science and technology create value and can drive economic recovery and future resilience.

The Market Uptake Process May 2023

Organised as a HYBRID event in Akure Nigeria by ECA on May 2023

Workshop organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator: Nwanne [ECA]

Facilitators: ECA team

Invited speakers/trainers: TBD

Rapporteur: Husseinat, ECA

Target groups / Participants

DIHs representatives, representatives from academia and the private sector including start-ups and government representatives. Most of the participant's organization operate within Africa- Nigeria specifically Akure, Lagos, Abuja. (Online participants can operate from anywhere in the world). Engagement of participants through open calls via local media and direct invitations through emails.

Venue and other organisational aspects

The Dome

Training material to be used

PowerPoint presentations; case studies; Canvases for technology transfer; Best practical examples from DIHs.

Draft Agenda

The agenda will cover the following topics: The engagement phase with technology; the phase for locating technology partners; the deal-making and negotiation phase; technology transfer contracts; licence agreements; spin-off; monitoring etc.

#38 Webinar: Digital Innovation Hubs Sustainability

June 2023

Organised online by ITC on 7 June 2023

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator/facilitator: tbc

Invited speakers/trainers: DIH specialist; sustainable development specialist.

Rapporteur: From ITC; In the registration form, a specific field to give consent to record the session and take pictures is going to be included;

Target groups / Participants

50 participants invited (target 15 participants) representing DIHs managers, startups and corporates from Africa and Europe. In this webinar, participants shall be introduced to the sustainability of the business, mainly how to achieve sustainability by creating and capturing values. DIHs generate value by providing a complete set of services and connecting different stakeholders. For that reason, those stakeholders are also welcomed to participate.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also through direct invitations from partners.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom; No interactive sessions are planned

Training material to be used

The material used will be mainly a PowerPoint presentation but additional material such as videos and case studies (ready to use training resources) may be used if the trainer considers them relevant. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda

To be defined by the trainer; The focus will be on defining sustainability, sustainability in DIHs, the importance of sustainable development.

#39 Webinar: Navigating through the Intellectual Property maze

June 2023

Organised online by PBS, in June 2023

Webinar organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator: There is a need for an external moderator with specific expertise in the topic. Profile: Technology transfer officers from Universities; IP managers.

Facilitators: Someone from PBS team or someone selected by them

Invited speakers/trainers: Telmo Vilela or Anabela Carvalho (tbc)

Rapporteur: In the registration form, a specific field to give consent to record the session and take pictures is going to be included;

Target groups / Participants

50 participants will be invited (target 15 participants) representing DIHs managers from Africa. This webinar is designed to specifically help participants navigate the procedural issues and the practical aspects of implementing an IP Management strategy, as well as enhance compliance with specific legislation. It is very specific, so the target is only African DIH. Participants will be engaged through open call invitations and invitations sent by partners in their existing communities.

Venue and other organisational aspects

Zoom; Mentimeter/ Jamboard; Breakout rooms

Training material to be used

The material used will be mainly a PowerPoint presentation but additional material such as videos and case studies (ready to use training resources) may be used if the trainer considers them relevant. All resources will be found on the project's online repository.

Draft Agenda

TBD; Focus on IP acquisition, IP exploitation, IP monitoring and IP enforcement

**#40 Webinar: Bridging the gap between offline and online marketing
June 2023**

Organised online by ATBN, with the help of YMH, in June 2023

Webinar organisation and facilitation team :

Main moderator/facilitator/ rapporteur: tbc

Invited speakers/trainers: Experience in digital marketing, having worked on building brand identity, being aware of social media management, marketing trends tools and strategies.

Target groups / Participants

60 participants will be targeted representing DIH Professionals, Youth, Start-ups , Digital Marketers in DIHs. The focus of the webinar will be the shift from offline to online marketing; Importance of digital marketing; Good practices of using digital marketing.

Participants will be from any country, 70% of them must come from Africa. Participants will be engaged through open invitations through the project website; social media and newsletters. Also through direct invitations from partners.

Zoom; Jam boards

Training material to be used

Videos, case studies, PowerPoint presentations, polls, sharing good practices; etc.

Draft Agenda

The webinar includes several topics. The first topic is the basic Digital Marketing principles so the participants can understand better how it works, what is included in Digital Marketing, so it is easier for them to implement it in their businesses. The second topic is about a digital marketing plan and learning how to structure it better, what to include and how to adapt it in their working environment. The third topic is about learning digital marketing tools that can support their businesses and learn in practice how to use them and identify which tools work better for their businesses.

#41 Local Workshop: Digital marketing for successful businesses (*Designing an accelerator*)

June 2023

Organised as a HYBRID event in Kampala (Uganda) by Outbox, in June 2023

Workshop organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator: Andrew Tugume

Andrew supports Outbox with regards to digital skilling initiatives for micro and small businesses under the Outbox EDU initiative.

Over the last eight years, Andrew has provided talent development skills training for various initiatives in Uganda with a focus on digital technologies. These have ranged from software development to digital marketing tools and techniques.

Invited speakers/trainers: The following speakers will be invited to the event:

- **Rebecca Mincy** is the Director at the Acumen Resilient Agriculture Fund. She has previously managed Acumen's portfolio of Agricultural businesses in East Africa.
- Michael Kasingye will support with the online training facilitation

Rapporteur: Rahmah Nampala : Rapporteur to undertake the note taking exercise

Target groups / Participants

- Two members from each of the Digital Innovation hubs under AfriconEU
 - Digital Innovation Hubs in Uganda (Start-up Uganda association and others): Approx 13 members will attend from mid-level management or investment analysts from members
- The initiative will target to host up-to 50 participants.

Venue and other organisational aspects

The event will be hosted at Outbox offices. Virtual participants will use Zoom for participation.

Training material to be used

- Mural for the online audience
- Whiteboards, flipcharts for the in-person engagement
- Slack channel for conversations

Draft Agenda

Time	Content/Process	Who
<i>Before the event</i>		
1 month to training	Self-assessment of potential attendees on their capacity to support start-ups with digital marketing	Andrew Tugume
2 weeks to training	Pre-reading material on digital marketing	Andrew Tugume
1 week to training	Pre-training case study assignment on the workshop	Andrew Tugume
<i>Training day</i>		
9:00 (20 minutes)	Welcome and introductions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participants online and in-person - Housekeeping instruction - Overview of the AfriconEU initiative - Focus of the training 	Perez Masinde
9.50 (50 minutes)	Introduction to Digital marketing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview of digital marketing landscape 	Andrew Tugume
10.00 (40 minutes)	Case study: Building a digital marketing strategy anchored in a business model	Andrew Tugume
10.40 (30 minutes)	Break	
11.10 (1 hour)	Deep dive into digital marketing tools for startups	Andrew Tugume
12.10 40 minutes	Case study exercise on digital tools for startups	Andrew Tugume
12.50	Debrief and wrap-up	Andrew Tugume // Perez Masinde

#42, #43, #44, #45: Design thinking bootcamps

July 2023

Organised by ECA in Nigeria, Hapa in Ghana, Outbox in Uganda and Buni in Tanzania on July 2023

Bootcamp organisation and facilitation team

Main moderator/ facilitators: AfriConEU Partners – Outbox, ECA, Hapa and Buni will be the key partners moderating or facilitating the bootcamps, as the main organisers of the activities. It is expected to be necessary to involve 5-6 facilitators per bootcamp.

Invited speakers/trainers: Experts will be invited to address the topics of the “Day Zero” of bootcamps. Experts might be also invited to deliver some of the “design thinking” activities of Days 1, 2 or 3. In Day 3, bootcamps’ participants will be challenged to present their ideas to users / investors; thus, users and investors shall be invited for the third day of the bootcamps.

Rapporteur: AfriConEU Partners – Outbox, ECA, Hapa and Buni will be the main rapporteurs, taking care of photos, recordings, minutes, testimonies from participants. Bootcamps will take place physically; the hybrid format is being assessed and tested. INOVA+ will provide support, mostly remote support given the distance.

Target groups / Participants

The connections made during the International Brokerage Event will be further supported to continue and evolve with the organisation of 4 design thinking bootcamps that will take place in each one of the targeted African countries aiming to bring together digital ecosystem stakeholders and experts from Europe and Africa and facilitate knowledge and experience sharing towards common projects development. The bootcamps will be also open to individuals not participating in the Brokerage Event. In more detail the target is to involve >40 participants in each bootcamp ensuring gender balanced, mixed teams of African and European DIH, Start-ups and enterprises.

Venue and other organisational aspects

TBD

Training material to be used

Moderators/ Facilitators and Speakers/ Trainers will be requested to use:

- AfriConEU training resources available at AfriConEU website³
- Design thinking techniques and tools, available for instance at Board of Innovation⁴ platform

Draft Agenda

The four bootcamps will follow the same structure. Nevertheless, the planned structure is sufficiently flexible to integrate any possible adjustment resulting from the local needs. The preliminary details of the bootcamps are presented next. Each bootcamp is planned as a **3+0 day** activity:

#Day 0 – the Getting Ready Day:

The first day of the bootcamp does not have a fixed date to occur. It translates an estimation of the time that bootcamps’ participants need to prepare – for the bootcamp challenges. The “Getting Ready Day” express a set of keynotes and other actions addressing the 4 sub-programmes of the

³ <https://www.africoneu.eu/training-resources-material/>

⁴ https://www.boardofinnovation.com/staff_picks/our-favorite-ideation-tools/

Trans-Continental Partnership Building Flagship Programme. These keynotes and activities will be organised as part of the Brokerage Event and/ or recorded after that event. As such, interested individuals have two main formats to access the activities composing the “Getting Ready Day”: one is through participation in the Brokerage Event, and another is by watching the recordings. To watch the recordings no registration will be necessary. To attend the 3-day bootcamp, interested individuals will need to register by completing an online form that will ask about personal contacts and a set of questions that will support the AfriConEU team to prepare the matching to form the teams during the bootcamps (which needs? Which interests and objectives for the bootcamp? Which ideas, if any, for a potential project? Etc.).

Format of Sub-programmes Presentation to be held during, preferably, Brokerage Event		
What?	Description	Time
Presentation of the 1st Sub-programme:		
<i>Towards a common digital market and a connected start-up ecosystem</i> (Talk with an expert)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Context - Challenges & Opportunities - Legal, cultural and language barriers - Example of concrete collaborations (sharing good practices) - Network channels - Practices to avoid: Lessons learned from Europe and Africa - Platforms to promote Africa-Europe collaboration and its features (funding opportunities, networking) 	50min
Suggestion of problems to be addressed by the 1st sub-programme to motivate discussion by stakeholders: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Practical ways to connect both ecosystems - Design a joint project for improving start-up’s support and digitalisation - How to engage the grassroots? 		
Presentation of the 2nd Sub-programme:		
<i>Digitalisation, jobs for the 21st century and employment opportunities</i> (Talk with an expert)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evolving labour market - Presentation of the 21st century skills/ competences of the future - Leadership - Communication - Co-creation - Team Working & Interpersonal Effectiveness - Technological Know-how in areas like AI, deeptech, hardware 	10 min
Suggestion of problems to be addressed by the 2nd sub-programme to motivate discussion by stakeholders: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to solve youth and women main challenges in the employment world? - Design an incentive model that is not merely economic for both continents to collaborate - Design a joint programme for competence development - How can the talent be attracted and retained? - How can the skills’ supply and demand be matched between continents? 		
Introduction to the 3rd Sub-programme:		
<i>Business and investment opportunities in the African market</i> (Talk with an expert)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview of the African market - Business partnerships (Europe-Africa, Africa-Africa) - Funding and investment opportunities - Shared funding, Exchange programs - Real examples 	35 min

Suggestion of problems to be addressed by the 3rd sub-programme to motivate discussion by stakeholders:

- How can we prevent brain drain?
- How to pitch to local investors?
- How to search for business and investment opportunities?
- How to access investor networks?
- How can African Diaspora know opportunities to invest back in their countries?

Introduction to the 4th Sub-programme:

Scouting digital entrepreneurs and start-ups in the African market (Talk with an expert)	<p>Defining digital entrepreneurs and their skills</p> <p>Challenges for African start-ups to enter the market:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Infrastructures and skills gap - Lack of enabling policies - Lack of trust, - Information gap <p>The role of the African Diaspora in building sustainable start-ups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - investor and start-up matching activities - innovation showcases and presentations - network with African diaspora groups and individuals - open calls for funding (cascade funding) - structured investment funds to bring trust - platforms for exchanges 	25min
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Suggestion of problems to be addressed by the 4th sub-programme to motivate discussion by stakeholders:

- Where can digital entrepreneurs be found?
- What are the most suitable activities for enterprises and start-ups/ entrepreneurs to collaborate? Mentoring?
- How can African start-ups pilot their solutions in the European context?

#Day 1 – the Ideation Day (~6,5 hours):

The first day of the bootcamp will be dedicated to motivating participants to know each other and to explore potential ideas for their projects. The agenda will be, thus, focused on networking and design thinking activities.

What?	Description	Time
Welcome	Presentation of the bootcamp programme, its objectives and expected results <i>– by AfriConEU partner</i>	10 min
Inspirational speech	Setting the scene for the African-European partnerships in a DIH perspective <i>– by AfriConEU partner or guest involved in a successful case of Africa-Europe cooperation</i>	10min
Warm-up	- 30-seconds pitch self-presentation (name, organisation and role in the organisation) <i>– by participants</i>	25 min
Networking	Possible formats: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - coffee-break with free talking style; - challenge: participants are challenged to interact with the maximum number of participants and ask them 2-3 questions to know more about their experience and what they look for during the bootcamp, people with more interactions win a symbolic prize; 	40 min

	– with participants	
Mapping	Mapping of expertise and objectives of participants, based on the information collected by participants in the previous activity – by facilitator, with the support of participants – Suggested tools: mind map, post its,	60 min
Lunchtime (90 min) All participants are invited to lunch in the same place and continue interacting.		
Warm-up	Setting up teams (8-10 teams)	20 min
Teamwork	Definition of the problem and project ideas per team – by participants, with support of facilitators who will guide participants in implementing ideation tools. – Ideation techniques' suggested tools: brainstorming, world café – No break will be organised. To provide coffee and snacks during the activity.	150 min

Day 2 – the Consolidation Day (~6 hours):

The second day of the bootcamp shall stimulate the consolidation of the ideas generated the day before. For this reason, the agenda will be focused on implementing design thinking activities that support participants to develop more their ideas. Furthermore, participants shall start preparing the information to be shared on the third day of the bootcamp.

What?	Description	Time
Warm-up	Presentation of the second-day agenda, its objectives and expected results + Ice breaker – by AfriConEU partner	15 min
Teamwork	Consolidating problem and project idea <i>Suggested tools: brainstorming, world café</i> – by participants, with support of facilitators who will guide participants in implementing ideation tools. – Ideation techniques' suggested tools: brainstorming, world café – No break will be organised. To provide coffee and snacks during the activity.	115 min
Lunchtime (90 min) All participants are invited to lunch in the same place and continue interacting.		
Teamwork	Ideation synthesis – by participants, with the support of facilitators who will guide participants in implementing tools. – Suggested tools: cluster, dot voting, ideation matrix	60 min
Teamwork	Concept and Project definition and prototyping: preparing the next day – by participants, with the support of facilitators – Suggested tools: idea napkin, concept canvas, business model canvas, wizard of oz. wireframes, cardboard	150 min

Day 3 – the Presentation Day (~7 hours):

The third and final day of the bootcamp will encourage participants to share their projects with the other participants and share feedback. Investors and other relevant stakeholders will be invited to this day to provide feedback to the teams.

What?	Description	Time
Warm-up	Presentation of the third-day agenda, its objectives and expected results	10 min

	<i>– by AfriConEU partner</i>	
Pitch #1	Presentation of Teams projects ideas / prototypes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 7 min presentation per project/ team. - 7 min feedback from other participants through an online tool (such as mentimeter, sli.do or other). The facilitator shall prepare the online tool with 2-3 questions for each of the teams of the bootcamp. The questions shall be the same (e.g. Main strengths of the project? Issues to be improved?) <i>– by participants</i>	150 min
Lunchtime (60 min)		
All participants are invited to lunch in the same place and continue interacting.		
Pitch #2	Pitch to real users and investors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 7 min presentation per project/ team. - 7 min feedback from users and investors invited to the bootcamp <i>– by participants and external stakeholders</i>	150 min
Towards the future	Closing Session + Networking Closing Session, wrapping up the bootcamp and launching the last networking moment to foster collaboration and explore the feedback from users and investors. <i>– with participants and external stakeholders</i>	60 min
Expected results: +30 ideas/prototypes co-designed for joint projects with African-EU partners (~7-8/ bootcamp);		

Activity #46: Final AfriConEU Capitalization Event

October 2023

Organised by DP in October 2023

Given the timeline for the Final Capitalization Event, the loose framing provided in the grant proposal, and the fact that the event is framed as a means of tying together, celebrating, and building on the other components of the networking academy, DP as the organizer of the Final Capitalization Event, requested to postpone the formal planning process for the event until October 2022, that is month 21 of the project, one year before the expected event, and following the majority of the work of the networking academy, in particular the Brokerage Event, which will inform the planning, content and structure of the Final Capitalization Event as the other major event foreseen in the program.

Broadly speaking, the event will be designed as a closure for the Academy program. It will be a multi-day event with **at least 400 participants**. It may include a range of features, such as brief recaps of elements from the other elements of the Academy program, contributions from other representatives of the ICT-58 Family, collaborative projects, and interactive sessions to propose and discuss projects that will carry forward the work from the AfriConEU project and other actors working in parallel.

The event may be organized in parallel with or as a component of a larger tech and innovation event, which would allow it to leverage an existing community of actors and deliver greater visibility.

The involvement of the other ICT-58 family projects would be a useful component to consider, since they could provide added context and opportunities related to the direct work of AfriConEU. In that case, the event would represent a conclusion not only of the AfriConEU networking academy, but of the work of the other projects.

Pending the formal planning activities, the following information and feedback gathering activities would be of value:

- Discussion of general guidelines and suggestions for potential content for the event.
- Expectations in terms of additional KPIs or objectives that might provide added focus.
- Feedback, outcomes, and materials from the networking academy events (especially audio-visual content that can help in creating summary content).
- Speakers or participants from the networking academy events (or other activities) that might be interesting to propose as participants or speakers in the capitalization event.
- Proposals for the format and organization of the potential event.

By collecting this information over the course of the first half of the Academy process (approximately months 14-21) a clearer picture of the Capitalization Event project will emerge, and a full project plan can be planned within 1 year prior to the final event.

4. Follow-up, monitoring and assessment

A key element for organising effectively and successfully the AfriConEU activities and events concerns their proper monitoring and assessment, which should be designed well in advance. Therefore, to ensure that the quality of all the planned activities and events is tracked, a monitoring and assessment strategy will be implemented throughout the delivery of all AfriConEU activities. Specifically, once each AfriConEU activity/event is finished, the partner organising the activity is required to perform the following follow up activities:

Table 10 - Follow up activities to be implemented after the end of each Academy activity/event

Follow up activities after the end of each Academy activity/event

Monitoring template [PARTNERS COORDINATING ACTIVITIES' ORGANISATION]

- ✓ **Fill in the Monitoring Template** (available in ANNEX 3: Post Activity Monitoring template) which is a tool for collecting essential information (i.e. participants' data, photos, testimonies etc.) about the activity delivered.
- ✓ **Send the Monitoring Template** to Stimmuli and YMH. Stimmuli will use it for the assessment and evaluation task while YMH will use it for the dissemination task.

Monitoring File [PARTNERS COORDINATING ACTIVITIES' ORGANISATION]

- ✓ **Fill in the Monitoring File** (created by INOVA) available in the project's MS Teams folder that was created under Task 5.1 with the aim of registering all relevant data about the stakeholders that engage with the AfriConEU activities (participants, moderators, speakers and/or other intervenients). This will help the consortium to have a better view of what type of community is being engaged in the project.

Evaluation Form [PARTNERS COORDINATING ACTIVITIES' ORGANISATION]

- ✓ **Circulate to participants and invited trainers/ speakers the Evaluation Form** to collect their feedback and impressions about the activity. In the case of online activities, evaluation forms will be shared online. In the case of physical activities, organisers may also distribute the printed forms directly to participants. *TIP: circulate the forms in the last minutes of the activity, so participants and speakers can quickly provide feedback.*
- ✓ Custom evaluation forms will be developed for each activity and will be provided by Stimmuli to those partners delivering the activities.

➔ To consult Stimmuli for the evaluation forms and the overall monitoring and evaluation process.

The monitoring template and the evaluation forms are the most important tools for assessing if the objectives of the AfriConEU Academy have been reached and to what extent. In addition, these tools will support the tracking of the project's KPIs, milestones and risks. On this basis, the next sections focus on presenting the KPIs that will be monitored together with the most critical Milestones, Risks and Mitigation actions for ensuring the smooth and unhindered implementation of the AfriConEU Academy activities.

4.1. Key Performance Indicators

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are the key indicators of progress made toward the intended outcomes and impact of the AfriConEU project. KPIs provide focus for operational improvement during the planning and implementation phase of the project and create an analytical basis for future decision making. Tracking KPIs is essential for the effective implementation of the planned activities since they will allow partners to keep track and evaluate the implementation, provide objective evidence of progress towards the set objectives as well as the general AfriConEU project objectives. Tracking the KPIs will provide a way to calculate the degree of change of all AfriConEU stakeholders involved in the AfriConEU Academy Programmes over time. It is essential to present the KPIs in this deliverable, to make sure all partners organizing and supporting activities and events are aware of them. Most importantly, the monitoring of the KPIs should be included in the implementation planning so that **a)** all appropriate evaluation data can be collected on time and **b)** partners follow a common way to monitor the implementation of all activities.

The following table presents the most important KPIs for tracking the progress of the implementation activities. Some KPIs were defined from the project's conception phase and some additional ones have been developed to help with the monitoring activity.

Table 11 - Key Performance Indicators of AfriConEU Networking Academy

Activity	Key Performance Indicator	Target
Capacity building webinars	No. total webinars organized	20
	No. participants (>70% from Africa)	>300 (>210)
	No. participants per webinar (>70% from Africa)	>15 (>10)
	No. external trainers and speakers (per webinar)	>20 (>1)
Local networking and knowledge sharing workshops	No. workshops organized	12
	No. total participants	>200
	No. participants per local workshop	>18
Repository of capacity building resources	No. repositories created	1
	No. resources added to the repository	>60
	No. resources used in the Academy activities	>46
International Brokerage event	No. Brokerage Events organized	1
	No. total attendees in the Brokerage Event	>200
	No. African DIHs to attend the Brokerage event	>10
	No. connections for strategic partnerships between African DIHs and EU Innovation stakeholders made during the event	>10
	No. participants from African Diaspora communities	>10
Design Thinking Bootcamps	No. bootcamps organized	4
	No. total participants	>160
	No. participants in each bootcamp	>40
	No. co-designed ideas/prototypes for joint projects with EU partners (per bootcamp)	>30 (>7)
Online Masterclasses for	No. masterclasses organized	8
	No. external speakers (per masterclass)	>8 (>1)
	No. total attendees (>70% from Africa)	>200

supporting African DIHs	No. attendees per masterclass	>25
Capitalisation event	No. total participants	>400

4.2. Milestones

The AfriConEU milestones are important tools that maximize partners productivity and assist in keeping the project implementation on track. With the implementation milestones that are cited in the following table, AfriConEU partners can easily identify what needs to be done to achieve the Academy implementation objectives. Milestones also assist in keeping track of what and when each project partner must do in each phase. AfriConEU milestones included in the following table are a result of a participatory planning meeting where all partners have contributed with their ideas.

Table 12 - Milestones of AfriConEU Networking Academy: official and intermediary

	Milestone Name	Expected Date	Means of verification	Reporting expected date	Official reporting	
	M1	Completion of the collaborative design process	Fev'22 M13	Shared document among all partners that includes everyone's inputs. <i>This milestone was reached in 07/02/2022</i>	Fev'22 M13	
Local Workshops	M2 MS7	Implementation of local networking and knowledge sharing workshops: 1 st local workshop delivered	May'22 M16	Monitoring Template completed (annex 3) + Agenda of workshops published on the website	May'22 M16	<i>EC portal</i>
	M3	Completion of the first 6 Local Workshops	Jan'22 M24	Monitoring Template completed (annex 3)	Fev'23 M25	
	M4 MS13	Local workshops delivered	Jun'23 M29	Monitoring Template completed (annex 3) + D4.3 Networking and knowledge sharing events report	Jul'23 M30	<i>EC portal</i>
Webinars	M5 MS8	1 st Webinar delivered	May'22 M16	Monitoring Template completed (annex 3) + Recording of the webinar available in podcast	Jun'22 M17	<i>EC portal</i>
	M6	First 10 Webinars delivered	Dec'22 M23	Monitoring Template completed (annex 3)	Jan'23 M24	
	M7 MS12	Last Webinar delivered	Jun'23 M29	Monitoring Template completed (annex 3) + D4.4 Webinars report	Jul'23 M30	<i>EC portal</i>
Brokerage Event	M8 MS9	Implementation of International Brokerage Event	Oct'22 M21	Monitoring Template completed (annex 3) + D4.5 Brokerage event report	Nov'22 M22	<i>EC portal</i>
Masterclasses	M9 MS15	1 st Masterclass delivered	Jun'22 M17	Monitoring Template completed (annex 3) + Programme of the online masterclass published on the website	Jul'22 M18	<i>EC portal</i>
	M10	First 6 Masterclasses delivered		Monitoring Template completed (annex 3)	M25	
	M11 MS17	Last Masterclass delivered	Apr'23 M27	Monitoring Template completed (annex 3) + D4.7 Online Masterclass report	May'23 M28	<i>EC portal</i>

Bootcamps	MS14	Implementation of 4 Design Thinking Bootcamps	Mar'23 M26	Programme of the bootcamps published on the website	Mar'23 26	<i>EC portal</i>
	M12 MS16	Design Thinking Bootcamps delivered	Jul'23 M30	Monitoring Template completed (annex 3) + D4.6 Design Thinking Bootcamps report	Ago'23 M31	<i>EC portal</i>
	M13	International Capitalisation and Celebration event delivered	Oct'23 M33	Monitoring Template completed (annex 3) + D4.8 Capitalisation and Celebration Event Report	Nov'23 M34	<i>EC portal</i>

4.3. Risks and mitigation actions

This section presents all the potential risks that have been identified by partners for each AfriConEU Academy activity event. Risk management is an essential part of the planning process to ensure the consortium can respond quickly and appropriately to any risks and challenges by developing the right strategies to eliminate or mitigate them. Therefore, the following table have been developed with inputs from all partners to ensure the inclusion of risks and measures relevant to both Europe and Africa and any needs based on the local context. This table will be consulted during the preparation phase of each activity and will be updated after the delivery of the activity with potential new risks and mitigation measures.

Table 13 - Risks and mitigation measures that can occur during AfriConEU Networking Academy
(H: High; M: Medium; L: Low)

Activity	Risks	Impact on Project			Probability			Mitigation Measure
		H	M	L	H	M	L	
Capacity Building Webinars	Limited participation		✓			✓		Early outreach and consortium network leverage. Direct outreach. Open registration. Second round role-filling.
	Availability of digital infrastructure		✓			✓		Sessions will be recorded and sent by request.
Local workshops in Ghana, Nigeria, Tanzania and Uganda	Limited participation		✓			✓		Early outreach and consortium network leverage. Direct outreach. Open registration. Second round role-filling.
	Availability of digital infrastructure		✓			✓		Sessions will be recorded and sent by request.
	Covid-19			✓			✓	Social distancing protocols will be taken onboard, and relevant local event protocols will be followed. Information for contact tracing will be collected
International Brokerage event	Covid restrictions may restrict travel within or between Europe and Africa and put other restrictions		✓			✓		Plan hybrid options and alternative timelines.
	Regional restrictions may limit capacity of venues			✓			✓	Consider extended event schedules, options for secondary venues and plan for alternative events
	Vaccination requirements may		✓			✓		Ensure early outreach and information on vaccine requirements. For speakers

Activity	Risks	Impact on Project			Probability			Mitigation Measure
		H	M	L	H	M	L	
	preclude participants from Africa							and invited participants, consider vaccination as prerequisite for covering their travel costs.
	Green Pass system offers limited interoperability with extra European health structures			✓		✓		Ensure early outreach and information on certification requirements. Develop appropriate systems to ensure certification for extra-European participants.
	Onsite exposure risks			✓			✓	Gather contact information for all onsite participants. Require vaccination and testing prior to attendance. Have emergency plan in case of exposure
	Limited participation	✓					✓	Early outreach and consortium network leverage. Direct outreach. Open registration. Second round role-filling.
	Lack of continuity between the Networking Academy and Brokerage Event	✓					✓	Focus on inviting participants from earlier events to take part in brokerage event. Reports on continuity of participants from the other Academy events. Early invitation process. Gap filling phase in speaker invitations. Close collaboration with consortium members in finding speakers.
	Difficulty finding speaker to meet verticals or transversal themes		✓				✓	Speed dating with onsite bookings. Direct matchmaking for potential collaborations. Pre-event introductions
	Low outcomes in terms of deal flow		✓				✓	Leveraging consortium networks (especially African partners); Direct outreach; Second round role-filling
	Lack of diversity of sector			✓			✓	Early outreach; Specialized branding and framing; Direct outreach; Second round role filling
	Failure of remote participation		✓				✓	Close collaboration with offsite partners; Test events prior to official event date; Independent offsite activities as stand-alone programs; Plan without over-reliance on remote activities.
	Failure to attract sponsors			✓		✓		Allow for an event that progresses without outside sponsorship; Plan for lower-level sponsor packages as needed
Speaker cost overruns						✓	Focus on local speakers when possible; Shift funding as needed from unused travel resources.	
Design Thinking Bootcamp in Nigeria, Ghana,	Limited participation		✓				✓	Early outreach and consortium network leverage. Direct outreach. Open registration. Second round role-filling.
	Availability of digital infrastructure			✓			✓	Plans for hybrid sessions are foreseen

Activity	Risks	Impact on Project			Probability			Mitigation Measure
		H	M	L	H	M	L	
Uganda, Tanzania	Covid-19		✓				✓	All activities will be implemented following the local COVID-19 regulations in place at the time
	Possible high cost of traveling to Africa			✓			✓	Hybrid format will be implemented (where that is possible)
	Stakeholders do not find usefulness/ advantage of taking part in bootcamps		✓				✓	AfriConEU partners have designed bootcamps based on the needs identified by African stakeholders. Participants will be also challenged to present their ideas/ prototypes to invited users/ investors, which might give them the opportunity to further explore and develop their ideas in the future.
	Participants do not produce the expected ideas/ prototypes (~7-8 per bootcamp).	✓					✓	AfriConEU partners will make sure the necessary techniques and tools will be listed and implemented during the bootcamps to guide and motivate participants to generate ideas and prototypes. Whenever possible, experts will be invited to raise the bootcamps contents quality.
Online Master classes	Limited participation		✓				✓	Early outreach and consortium network leverage. Direct outreach. Open registration. Second round role-filling.
	Availability of digital infrastructure			✓			✓	Sessions will be recorded and sent by request

5. Implementation team members and responsibilities

The last section of this deliverable is focused on defining clear roles and responsibilities among all partners involved in the roll out implementation of the 46 different Academy activities and events. In complex projects, such as AfriConEU, it is essential to clarify all partners role to avoid confusion, increase efficiency and ensure that all the right mechanisms are in place for a successful implementation.

As illustrated in the following figure, partners form two main teams. The first team of partners is responsible for the overall coordination and support of the implementation activities and the second team is responsible for the actual delivering of the implementation activities. Within these two teams each partner has distinct roles and responsibilities.

Figure 7 - Partners roles and responsibilities in AfriConEU Networking Academy

The Coordination and Support team includes five main roles:

- The Overall Implementation Coordinator (INOVA+)
- The Implementation Planning and Assessment Leader (Stimmuli)
- The Community Engagement Leader (ECA)
- The Dissemination Leader (YMH)

The Implementation team includes the organizers and designers of each Academy Activity and Events. Both teams will have a close collaboration and interaction during the implementation activities. For instance, partners from the Coordination Team will also contribute to the delivery of the Academy Activities. Partners from the Implementation Team will contribute to the dissemination, monitoring and assessment activities of the Coordination

and Support Team. The following table provides a more detailed description of each partner's role and responsibility during implementation.

Table 14 - Partners roles and responsibilities in AfriConEU Networking Academy: detailed description

Partner	Contact person	Responsibilities	
		Organizing	Supporting
INOVA	Ana S. Leal Ana Aleixo Tânia Moreira Marta Coto	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Coordinating all the implementation activities ✓ Develop the strategy & methodology for the design thinking bootcamps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Target engagement activities to European stakeholders ✓ Contribute to webinar delivery ✓ Actively support DP with International Brokerage Event
Stimmuli	Magda Bakali Irene Kalemaki	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Coordinating the monitoring and evaluation of all implementation activities ✓ 1 Masterclass (with ITC) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Target engagement activities to European stakeholders ✓ Contribute to webinar delivery
ECA	Peace Odili	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 3 local workshops in Nigeria ✓ 1 design thinking bootcamp in Nigeria ✓ Developing the engagement strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Engagement of African stakeholders ✓ Contribute to webinar delivery
YMH	Marilena Maragkou	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Dissemination activities for all Academy activities and events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Engagement Activities to European stakeholders ✓ Contribute to webinar delivery
ATBN	Eunice Ball	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 10 Webinars 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Target engagement activities to European stakeholders
PBS	Catarina Reis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 5 Webinars ✓ 1 Masterclass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Target engagement activities to European stakeholders
Hapa	Gideon Brefo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 3 local workshops in Ghana ✓ 1 design thinking bootcamp in Ghana 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Engagement of African stakeholders ✓ Contribute to webinar delivery
Outbox	Perez Masinde Richard Zulu	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 1 design thinking bootcamp in Uganda ✓ 3 local workshops in Uganda 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Engagement of African stakeholders ✓ Actively support DP with International Brokerage Event
Buni	Patience Abraham Hub Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 3 workshops in Tanzania ✓ 1 design thinking bootcamp in Tanzania 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Engagement of African stakeholders ✓ Contribute to webinars delivery
DP	Joseph Gaylord	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Brokerage event ✓ International Celebration and Capitalisation Event 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Target engagement activities to European stakeholders ✓ Contribute to webinar delivery
ITC	Sasa Straus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 5 Webinars ✓ 7 Masterclasses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Target engagement activities to European stakeholders ✓ Contribute to webinar delivery

5.1. Implementation support mechanism

The implementation of the numerous activities of the AfriConEU Academy comes with a set of foreseeable challenges that may arise due to:

- Potential difficulties in coordination among partners;
- Time constrains;
- Lack of opportunity to collaborate with others doing similar work in the same region/country or in a trans-continental level;
- Etc.

To face such challenges, partners have agreed to put in place an “implementation support mechanism” which is based on peer-to-peer experience sharing.

Peer-to-peer experience sharing is a simple learning format. Peer-to-peer refers to knowledge which is passed between co-workers, making learning easier and more relevant to everyone involved.

A peer-to-peer support mechanism, tailor-made for AfriConEU, is presented below. This mechanism is developed to encourage peer to peer sharing and get the partners from the two different continents to communicate and consult each other when needed. The thinking process behind the design of this mechanism follows the methodological approach of the whole AfriConEU project. It combines Collaborative Design Technique to bring together key stakeholders from two continents and engage them in the co-creation of two flagship programs. Similarly, the implementation support mechanism presented here is part of the Collaborative Design planning method applied in this deliverable that aims on encouraging peer to peer experience sharing and collaboration.

The suggested working groups presented below will meet after each Academy Activity to share experiences and ideas for improvement and encourage the exchange of diverse perspectives through transcontinental collaboration.

Table 15 - Schedule for running a peer-to-peer implementation support mechanism

Type of Activity	Partner involved	When	Means of communication	Purpose
Webinars	PBS, ATBN ITC, DP, Stimuli, INOVA	After each webinar	Online meeting	Technical and Content questions/concerns Discussion over what worked and what needs improvement Evaluation Forms Submission/Report
Local workshops	Buni, Hapa, ECA, Outbox, Stimuli, INOVA	After each workshop	Online meeting	Technical and Content questions/concerns Discussion over what worked and what needs improvement Evaluation Forms Submission/Report
International Brokerage event	DP , Stimuli, INOVA	After the event	Online meeting	Evaluation and exchange of comments Discussion over what worked or didn't work
Design Thinking Bootcamps	Buni+Hapa+ECA+ Outbox Stimuli, INOVA	After each Bootcamp	Online meeting	Technical and Content questions/concerns Discussion over what worked and what needs improvement Evaluation Forms Submission/Report
Online Masterclasses	Buni, Hapa, ECA, Outbox, ITC, Stimuli, INOVA	After each Masterclas s	Online meeting	Technical and Content questions/concerns Discussion over what worked and what needs improvement Evaluation Forms Submission
Capitalisation and celebration event	All partners	After the event	Online meeting	Discussion over what worked and what didn't Event Report/Evaluation Forms Submission

6. Conclusion

AfriConEU is an ambitious project for empowering African and European DIHs by delivering 46 training and networking activities in the coming months. These activities aim at fostering the sharing of knowledge, good practices, experiences and resources between DIHs in Africa and between DIHs in Africa and Europe, in a comprehensive, replicable and self-sustaining way.

This deliverable, which is a product of collaborative work among AfriConEU partners, was developed to support, organise and plan the implementation of these 46 activities and events. Therefore, this document is a useful and practical tool for the AfriConEU partners. It provides step-by-step guidelines for organising the AfriConEU Academy activities, engaging participants, and performing follow-up actions. It also includes useful templates, ready to be used by the AfriConEU partners for monitoring and assessing the success of the AfriConEU Academy activities.

In sum, this deliverable intends to be a tool for supporting partners to be better prepared and more efficient when implementing the AfriConEU Academy activities. At the same time, this document is flexible enough to be used by anyone else planning and implementing activities similar to those that will be delivered by the AfriConEU Networking Academy.

ANNEXES

ANNEX 1: Participant Invitation Email Template

Please find the AfriConEU Letterhead on Teams in WP6 Folder_T6.2 Project Branding

The first Trans-continental Networking Academy
for African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.

www.africoneu.eu | africoneu@inova.business | #AfriConEU

Dear Sir/Madame,

You are invited to [name and type of the event] organized [location/zoom/other platform] in [date]. The [Local Workshop/Webinar/Masterclass] is part of a series of events that constitute the [AfriConEU Networking Academy](#).

To register for our event please click here [insert link with registration form]

The Academy has two Flagship Programmes, the first one is the DIHs Capacity Building Programme and the second is the Transcontinental Partnership Programme. Both programmes are built around a variety of themes such as Business development, Technology Transfer, Start-Ups financial support and Digital and entrepreneurial skills development for professionals, youth and women. You are welcome to attend all of any of the AfriConEU Academy events. For more information, please visit our events section [here](#).

If you wish to subscribe to the AfriConEU Newsletter to receive news about the project activities, please click [here](#).

Sincerely,

[Name of organizer]

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016687.

ANNEX 2: Checklist for planning local activities

Early event planning	Deadline	Completed
Organisation and facilitation team		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Main moderator assigned 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ E-mail invitations to external speakers/ trainers/ facilitators sent 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ External speakers/trainers/facilitators assigned 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Rapporteur assigned 		
Invitations/call for participants		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Online registration form developed 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Invitation / call for participants composed 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mailing list of targeted participants generated 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Invitation / call for participants sent / goes live on social media 2 month before actual activity 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Participation process closes and a participant list together with reserve list is developed 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Names on list and titles/addresses checked for accuracy 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Attendance confirmation is completed 		
Logistics		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Date/s of event confirmed 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Location/venue for event booked/confirmed 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Speakers/Trainers who have accepted to attend are fully informed (double check in case of cancellations) 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Plan of presentation/activity/session completed 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ List of attendees ready and confirmed 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Program and Agenda finalized 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Final Agenda to confirmed attendees sent 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Needed equipment confirmed (computers, screens, power, cables, other materials such as notebooks, pens, highlighters) 		

ANNEX 3: Post Activity Monitoring Template

MONITORING FORM

FOR AFRICONEU PARTNERS (acting as ORGANISERS/ FACILITATORS)

1) Activity/ Event Overview	
Activity/ Event Title	
Date	
Organiser	
Location	
Number of participants	
Link to training materials used from the AfriconEU repository	
Summary of Activity/Event <i>(Refer to results achieved conclusions & impressions including also the scope, number and type of participants and training format)</i>	

2) Overview of Organising Team						
Moderators/facilitators						
Name	Email	Gender	Country of residence	Job title	Sector	Type of Organization
Trainer(s)/ Speaker(s)						
Name	Email	Gender	Country of residence	Job title	Sector	Type of Organization

3) Risk Management	
Risks occurred	
Mitigation actions taken	

4) Respond to the following statements depending on whether you agree or disagree.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree, nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
The level of my interaction and communication with the trainer(s)/ speaker(s) was very good	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The activity/ event successfully met its training and learning objectives	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The activity/ event stimulated participants' interest and interaction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

5) Respond to the following open-ended questions

What are the 3 most important items that made this activity/ event successful?	
What are the 3 most important items you would change for making this activity/ event more successful?	

6) Relevant KPIs achieved

(*please fill in ONLY 'Reached' Column)

	Target	Number reached
Capacity building webinars	No. total webinars organized	20
	No. participants (>70% from Africa)	>300 (>210)
	No. participants per webinar (>70% from Africa)	>15 (>10)
	No. external trainers and speakers (per webinar)	>20 (>1)
Local networking and knowledge sharing workshops	No. workshops organized	12
	No. total participants	>200
	No. participants per local workshop	>18
Repository of capacity building resources	No. repositories created	1
	No. resources added to the repository	>60
	No. resources used in the Academy activities	>46
International Brokerage event	No. Brokerage Events organized	1
	No. total attendees in the Brokerage Event	>200
	No. African DIHs to attend the Brokerage event	>10
	No. connections for strategic partnerships between African DIHs and EU Innovation stakeholders made during the event	>10
Design Thinking Bootcamps	No. bootcamps organized	4
	No. total participants	>160
	No. participants in each bootcamp	>40
	No. co-designed ideas/prototypes for joint projects with EU partners (per bootcamp)	>30 (>7)
Online Masterclasses for supporting African DIHs	No. masterclasses organized	8
	No. external speakers (per masterclass)	>8 (>1)
	No. total attendees (>70% from Africa)	>200
	No. attendees per masterclass	>25
Capitalisation event	No. total participants	>400

GENERAL KPI <i>Please identify how your event contributed to reach the following KPI (answer depending on the flagship programme of your event)</i>	Target Number	Number Reached	Explain your reached number
For Capacity Building Flagship activities:			
More than 1000 innovation stakeholders in Africa reached AfriConEu	1000		
More than 300 DIHs and innovation stakeholders directly trained by the programmes and build their skills in DIHs development and sustainability models, technology transfer services, business support services and access to funding for star-ups; Entrepreneurial and digital skills development for professionals, youth and women	300		
More than 200 DIHs improved their networks and connections with other hubs within local ecosystems and beyond through local networking events	200		
For Transcontinental Partnership Development Flagship activities:			
African DIHs gain access to European networks of investors and collaborators	>30		
European Investors and entrepreneurs get familiar with African markets opportunities in Africa;	>30		
New partnerships established with African diaspora communities in Europe for supporting further African start-ups and SMEs.	>10		

7) Checklist

(*Please send all attachments to maqda.bakali@stimmuli.eu)

1) Agenda and other information produced for the event attached	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) List of registered participants, <u>identifying who actually attended the event,</u> attached	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) Photos/ Screenshots attached	<input type="checkbox"/>
3) I have shared evaluation questionnaires with all participants and trainer(s)/ speaker(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>
4) Participant testimonies collected Please write quotes/testimonies from participants/trainer(s) here	<input type="checkbox"/> Testimony 1: Testimony 2: Testimony 3:

ANNEX 4: Agenda template

[Insert Organizing Partner's Logo]

Webinar Title

Time	Content/Process	Who
5 minutes	<p><u>Technology Check</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sound check 	
5 minutes	<p><u>Set-Up</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Welcome & Introductions ● Review of outcomes/purpose of the webinar 	
5 minutes	<p><u>Overview</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overview of the webinar ● Walk-through of documentation (if needed) 	
15 minutes	<p><u>Part 1 (Title of Topic)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deliver/Discuss ● Online Interaction/ Engagement 	
15 minutes	<p><u>Part 2 (Title of Topic)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deliver/Discuss ● Online Interaction/Engagement 	
10 minutes	<p><u>Wrap-Up</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Questions & answers 	
5 minutes	<p><u>Webinar Closure</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Closing Remarks ● Webinar Evaluation Form Reminder 	